

Bimetallic MOFs, their composites, and derivatives: synthesis strategies and structure–property relationships for supercapacitor applications

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ABSTRACT

Bimetallic metal–organic frameworks (BMOFs) have rapidly evolved into a powerful materials platform for next-generation supercapacitor (SC) electrodes by enabling atomic-level control, enhanced redox chemistry, tunable electronic structures, and pore architectures beyond the limits of monometallic frameworks. By co-incorporating two distinct metal centers within one crystalline lattice, BMOFs create synergistic metal–metal interactions that modulate d-band electronic states, generate flexible redox couples and promotes defect-rich coordination environments, collectively enhancing charge storage kinetics and active-site utilization. This review critically examines recent progress in BMOF design for SCs, emphasizing synthetic strategies that govern metal distribution, framework topology, hierarchical morphology, and compositional homogeneity. We discuss how dual-metal coordination and hierarchical porosity accelerate ion diffusion and charge transfer, while mitigating structural degradation during prolonged cycling. Particular attention is given to BMOF-based hybrid electrodes and BMOF-derived oxides, hydroxides, chalcogenides, and phosphides, where in situ framework conversion yields conductive, mechanically robust architectures with high pseudocapacitive activity. We further highlight how integration with advanced functional materials creates redox-active heterointerfaces that accelerate charge transfer, enhance active site utilization, and improve overall SC device performance. Finally, we highlight key bottlenecks including conductivity, scalability, and interfacial stability that must be addressed to translate BMOF-based materials into durable, high-energy SC devices.

1. Introduction

The accelerating global energy demand, together with the depleting fossil fuel reserves, poses mounting challenges for both environmental sustainability and energy security [1,2]. In response, large-scale deployment of renewable energy technologies has progressed rapidly, with global installed renewable power capacity exceeding 3.8 TW by the end of 2023, dominated by solar and wind energy [3]. Nevertheless, the intrinsic intermittency of these resources necessitates their integration with efficient and durable electrochemical energy storage (EES) systems

(e.g., supercapacitors, batteries, and hybrids thereof) to ensure grid reliability and supply continuity [4]. This need is further underscored by projections indicating that grid-scale energy storage capacity must increase by more than an order of magnitude by 2030 to support deep renewable penetration [5]. Furthermore, the continuous demand from mobile devices and data centres drives the need for sustainable EES that offer high performance, safety, and low cost [6]. Supercapacitors (SCs), also known as ultracapacitors, are advanced energy storage devices that bridge the gap between conventional capacitors and batteries. Unlike batteries, which store energy mainly through bulk chemical redox

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reactions, SCs store energy primarily through electric double-layer formation and/or fast surface redox processes at the electrode/electrolyte interface, enabling rapid charging/discharging [7]. This mechanism endows SCs with high-power density, superior cycling stability, and fast response time, making them promising for electric vehicles, renewable energy systems, and consumer electronics.

A typical SC device (Fig. 1a) consists of two electrodes separated by a porous membrane and immersed in an ion-conducting electrolyte. The electrodes are usually fabricated from porous materials with high surface area to facilitate faster adsorption of ions at the electrode/electrolyte interface. The electrodes are separated by a thin, porous membrane known as the separator that prevents direct electrical contact between the two electrodes while allowing the transport of ions through the electrolyte. The separator must possess excellent ionic permeability, chemical stability, and mechanical robustness under operating conditions to prevent short circuits and ensure the long-term reliability of the SC device. The electrolyte serves as the ion-conducting medium, enabling the movement of ions between electrodes during charging and discharging. The choice of electrolyte (aqueous, organic, or ionic) directly impacts the voltage window, ionic conductivity, and overall energy density of the SC device [8,9]. For instance, aqueous electrolytes offer high ionic conductivity and environmental friendliness but are typically limited due to a relatively narrow electrochemical stability window (1.0–1.23 V). In contrast, organic and ionic liquid electrolytes enable a wider voltage window, enhancing energy density, but their use is often limited by high cost, complex synthesis, and potential toxicity [8,9].

The choice of electrode material plays a critical role in determining the performance of an SC device. The physicochemical properties of the electrode material directly influence the charge storage mechanism, charge transport kinetics, rate capability, and cycling stability. To date, several types of electrode materials have been employed for SC applications, including carbon-based materials [10,11], metal oxides/sulfides [12,13], 2D transition metal dichalcogenides [14,15], conductive polymers [16,17], MXene(s) [18,19], and metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) [20,21], and their hybrids [22–26]. Among the different studied electrode materials, MOFs have gained significant attention in recent years owing to their high specific surface area (SSA), tunable porosity, and diverse chemical functionalities. MOFs are a rich family of crystalline porous materials constructed by connecting organic linkers (ligands) and metal nodes (secondary building units; SBUs) through coordination [27,28]. The physicochemical properties of MOFs largely depend on the combination of metal ions (Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Fe^{3+}) and organic linkers. The organic linkers are usually

aromatic polycarboxylates and nitrogen-containing compounds, which coordinate with the metal ions or clusters to form the extended networks [29]. The aromatic polycarboxylates contain multiple carboxylic acid groups ($-\text{COOH}$), which upon undergoing deprotonation readily form carboxylate groups ($-\text{COO}^-$). These $-\text{COO}^-$ groups coordinate to metal ions through oxygen atoms to form stable and robust MOFs. The aromatic rings also enhance $\pi-\pi$ interactions and contribute to structural stability and porosity. A few common examples of such linkers are terephthalic acid (benzene-1,4-dicarboxylic acid, H_2BDC), 2,6-naphthalenedicarboxylic acid (NDC), trimesic acid (benzene-1,3,5-tricarboxylic acid, BTC), and pyromellitic acid (benzene-1,2,4,5-benzenetetracarboxylic acid) [29]. On the other hand, nitrogen-containing linkers often consist of heterocyclic aromatic compounds with nitrogen donor atoms, which can coordinate to metal ions through lone pair electrons. A few examples of nitrogen-containing linkers are bipyridine, 1,10-phenanthroline, 2-aminobenzene-1,4-dicarboxylic acid, as well as various heterocyclic azoles (imidazole, triazole, tetrazole, pyrazole) and heterocyclic azines (adenine, pyridine, triazine, pyrazine, pyrimidine, tetrazine) [30]. The coordination of these N-containing linkers with the metal nodes results in stable MOF architectures with redox-active functionalities. Due to the diversity of organic linkers, MOFs can be designed in different dimensionalities (1D, 2D, or 3D), allowing precise control over porosity, ion transport channels, and electronic pathways. MOF structures with these unique properties have been widely used in diverse applications, including catalysis, sensing, drug delivery, gas storage and separation, environmental remediation, and energy storage and conversion [26,31,32].

Among these diverse applications, MOFs have gained significant attention for energy storage specifically in the field of SCs, owing to the intrinsic advantages of high SSA, tunable porosity, structure flexibility, and inherent electrochemical redox-active sites. Despite these advantages, MOFs generally suffer from limitations such as poor intrinsic electrical conductivity, low mechanical strength, and insufficient structural stability during repeated charge–discharge cycles, which restricts their direct applicability in energy storage devices [31,33–35]. Consequently, even with recent advancements, such as heterostructure construction with functional materials [34], rational structural engineering [36], and binder-free architectures [37], the electrochemical performance of pristine MOFs remains suboptimal for high-performance SC applications.

To overcome the existing challenges, a highly promising strategy involves the design of bimetallic MOFs (BMOFs), which incorporate two different metal nodes coordinated with organic linkers within a single framework. The synergistic interactions between the two metal centers

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic of a typical SC device and (b) publications per year on bimetallic MOFs for SC applications (Publication trends were obtained from OpenAlex and Scopus databases using the query ((bimetallic OR bimetal)) AND (“metal-organic framework” OR MOF)) AND (supercapacitor OR pseudocapacitor OR “energy storage”).

significantly enhance the electrical conductivity, structural stability, and redox activity of the framework. Consequently, BMOFs have emerged as next-generation electrode materials offering enhanced electrochemical performance for SC applications. Publications on BMOFs for SC applications have surged in recent years driven by advances that enable precise control over atomic arrangement and morphology (Fig. 1b). BMOFs are typically synthesized by incorporating two distinct metal ions into one crystalline network in tunable ratios, allowing precise control over their electronic structure, redox activity, and overall physicochemical properties [31,38,39]. Thus, BMOFs have been systematically applied as an electrode material for SC applications by leveraging their additional redox-active sites due to metal–metal cooperativity. To overcome the inherent limitations of MOFs, such as low electrical conductivity and limited ion transport, BMOFs have been integrated with conductive and functional materials including carbonaceous materials, MXenes, conducting polymers and layered double hydroxides (LDHs) to construct hybrid architectures [40–42]. Another widely adopted strategy is to derive advanced functional materials from BMOFs, such as mixed-metal oxides/hydroxides, sulfides/selenides/tellurides, phosphides and to further construct their hybrids, through thermal or chemical treatments. Moreover, the approach of obtaining functional materials by the direct carbonization/pyrolysis of BMOFs is promising due to their environmentally friendly synthesis routes and cost-effectiveness. Additionally, during the carbonization/pyrolysis of BMOFs, a synergistic transformation occurs wherein the organic linkers decompose to form in situ conductive carbon, while the metal centers are converted into electrochemically active metal-based nanostructures. The resulting BMOF-derived materials are uniformly embedded in and coated with a conductive carbon matrix, offering improved charge storage performance. These BMOF-derived materials (and their hybrids) typically show higher electrical conductivity and structural stability than their monometallic counterparts, while providing multiple redox-active centers and tunable interfacial chemistry, features that are advantageous for charge storage. Fig. 2 presents a schematic overview of representative BMOF-based materials, highlighting their diverse hybrid structures and morphologies along with the key parameters governing SC performance.

Only a few review articles have addressed the development of BMOFs and their derived materials, focusing broadly on the synthesis routes and electrochemical performance for SCs [30,34,35]. Distinct

from these reviews on BMOFs, this review adopts a mechanism-driven and multiscale perspective that connects atomic-level dual-metal coordination chemistry to framework architecture, electrode behavior, and device-level SC performance. Rather than benchmarking electrochemical metrics alone, we elucidate how synergistic metal–metal interactions, mixed-valence redox couples, and coordination-induced defect chemistry govern electronic structure, ion transport kinetics, and cycling stability. Furthermore, BMOFs are treated not only as functional electrodes but as programmable precursors whose composition, porosity, and coordination environment predetermine the phase evolution, conductivity and electrochemical activity of derived oxides, hydroxides, chalcogenides, and composite architectures. In addition, this review uniquely emphasizes electrolyte–framework co-design, demonstrating how electrolyte chemistry, ion solvation and pore hierarchy jointly regulate charge storage mechanisms and redox accessibility in bimetallic systems. By integrating synthesis, structure, transformation pathways and interfacial electrochemistry across length scales, this work establishes a multiscale structure–property roadmap for BMOF-based SC electrodes and provides a conceptual framework for rationally engineering high-performance, durable energy storage materials.

2. Recent development in BMOFs

Recent advancements in BMOFs have underscored their distinctive structural characteristics and their broad potential applications in catalysis, sensing, drug delivery, gas storage and separation, environmental remediation, and energy storage and conversion [26,31,32,43,44]. This section surveys the various synthetic approaches employed to develop BMOFs, highlighting how different methods govern their structure, morphology, and dimensionality. These features are then correlated with electrochemical behavior, emphasizing their suitability and potential as high-performance electrode materials for SC applications. Section 2.1 provides an overview of BMOF synthesis strategies, structural features, and intrinsic properties relevant to SC applications.

2.1. Synthetic strategies

The synthetic methodologies for preparing BMOFs are crucial for tailoring their structural and functional features. Compared with

Fig. 2. Schematic of BMOFs with the possibility of different structures, morphologies, and key factors governing the SC performance.

monometallic MOFs, BMOFs introduce greater complexity into the framework. The two metals can coordinate with each other and/or to the organic linkers in several ways (Fig. 3a). From a broad perspective, the synthesis of monometallic and bimetallic MOFs can be categorized into one-pot synthesis (also called direct synthesis) and post-synthetic modification (PSM), as shown in Fig. 3b. To date, numerous advances in synthesis strategies have focused on improving the physicochemical properties and stability, while enhancing raw material availability and economic sustainability (Fig. 3c). Furthermore, these strategies can be combined and/or adapted using approaches such as template-assisted synthesis, microwave-assisted synthesis, and biogenic routes [32,38,45,46]. Each approach has distinct features and advantages and can be selected according to the intended applications, as described in detail below.

2.1.1. One-pot synthesis (direct synthesis) and emerging approaches

The one-pot synthesis strategy incorporates two different metal ions simultaneously during the synthesis of BMOFs. For this purpose, metal precursors, i.e., salts or complexes of two different metals and organic linkers, are mixed in a single reaction environment. The reaction conditions, such as temperature, solvent, and pH, are then carefully optimized to ensure uniform integration of both metal ions in the framework. Because both precursors are introduced simultaneously, one-pot synthesis can yield relatively homogeneous metal distributions throughout the framework [42]. Nevertheless, the simultaneous incorporation of different metals may lead to competition or preferential bonding, and thus, there is a possibility of uneven distribution or incomplete integration. However, the simplicity of this approach facilitates scale up for bulk production of well-defined frameworks [56,57]. This direct synthesis strategy can be sub-divided into different methods for simultaneous incorporation of different metal ions. Such methods include hydrothermal/solvothermal methods, co-deposition/co-precipitation methods, mechanochemical routes, and other modified approaches for tuning BMOF properties.

One of the most common one-pot methods for synthesizing BMOFs is the solvothermal or hydrothermal approach. This methodology involves dissolving metal salts and organic linkers in a solvent, typically under elevated temperatures and pressures [58,59]. The solvent serves not only as a medium for dissolving precursors but also influences the crystallization process, leading to diverse structural morphologies. The choice of solvent and temperature can be critical. Under solvothermal conditions, polar organic solvents (e.g., DMF, methanol, ethanol) play multiple roles as reaction media, coordinative modulators, and crystal-

growth directors. They influence nucleation rates, ligand-deprotonation kinetics, framework topology, and porosity. For instance, solvents that stabilize different metal ions may lead to more homogeneous distribution. For example, NiCo BMOF was grown in situ on a carbon cloth substrate by using a one-step solvothermal reaction. The solvothermal reaction enabled the growth of a highly open NiCo-BTC nanosheets array on carbon cloth using a low toxicity alcoholic solution and the 1,3,5-benzenetricarboxylic acid (H₃BTC) organic linker [60]. In a study on Zn/Co bimetallic systems, the authors synthesized Zn/Co-MeIm MOFs via a controlled solvothermal conversion of hydroxy double salts (HDSs) [61]. By adjusting solvent composition, ligand choice, and reaction time, the authors tuned the crystal topologies from sodalite to diamond and obtained varied morphologies such as 2D nanosheets, rhombic dodecahedra and truncated cubes. Similarly, in another report, a Zn—Cu bimetallic MOF composite prepared by a solvothermal approach showed that introducing a secondary metal (Zn²⁺) into the Cu-BTC framework generates defects and synergistic interactions, which increase charge density and enhance textural properties such as SSA and pore distribution [62]. This technique has also shown efficient results for the synthesis of various BMOFs, allowing for high yields of crystalline materials [46,58]. These structural differences strongly influence SC performance by regulating SSA, pore architectures, electrolyte accessibility, ion-diffusion pathways, and redox-site utilization.

Co-deposition is another strategy that involves the simultaneous introduction of two different metal ions during the synthesis stage. This approach can be achieved through techniques such as co-precipitation. Co-precipitation occurs when metal salts, in the presence of organic linkers, precipitate simultaneously, resulting in the concurrent incorporation of both metals into the MOF structure [31,46]. This strategy can help achieve desired bimetallic ratios and is advantageous for producing frameworks with specific catalytic or adsorption properties. For instance, recent studies have demonstrated that controlling the metal deposition rates can lead to the formation of highly active catalysts for CO₂ capture and various other reactions [63,64]. In the work by Guo et al., the authors studied the simultaneous introduction of Zn²⁺ and Co²⁺ during the synthesis of bimetallic ZIF-8/67 frameworks via a co-precipitation type approach [65]. They found that differences in metal coordination kinetics led to distinct metal distributions. High Co/Zn ratios yielded homogeneous solid solutions, whereas lower ratios resulted in core-shell nanostructures due to preferential nucleation behavior. This demonstrates that co-deposition not only affects metal ratios but also crystal morphology and internal metal distribution,

Fig. 3. (a) Schematic of possibilities of metal-metal coordination in case of bimetallic MOF (Reproduced with permission [47] Copyright 2017, ACS), (b) schematic representation of monometallic and bimetallic MOFs with synthesis strategies, and (c) timeline of development of MOF synthesis approaches [48–54] (Reproduced with permission [55] Copyright 2024, Nature).

which can be tuned by changing precursor conditions and relative reactivities.

The mechanochemical route is a direct synthesis method for preparing BMOFs. It involves grinding metal salts and organic linkers together in a ball mill, leading to solid-state reactions that produce the desired MOF. This method is environmentally friendly because it avoids the use of solvents and can lead to rapid synthesis [66]. Mechanochemical synthesis has shown promise in BMOFs creation due to its ability to achieve uniform metal mixing and expedited reactions. Furthermore, this method allows for greater flexibility in selecting various metal combinations, which can result in unique frameworks not easily obtained through most conventional wet-chemical methods [64]. For instance, ZnCu MOF-74 was synthesized by following the ball milling method, demonstrated that mechanochemical treatment affects both structural order and catalytic behavior [67]. Although the ordered MOF-74 phase becomes partially amorphized under prolonged milling, the resulting material exhibits enhanced catalytic activity and selectivity for CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol relative to its monometallic counterparts. Fundamental studies of the mechanochemical formation of MOF-74 highlight complex intermediate phases that precede final crystallization, suggesting mechanochemistry follows distinct reaction pathways compared with conventional solvent-mediated synthesis [68].

Microwave-assisted synthesis is an innovative approach that has emerged due to its rapid and uniform heating capabilities. In this method, the constituents of the MOFs are subjected to microwave radiation, resulting in accelerated crystallization and often higher-quality MOFs than traditional methods [69]. The microwave method can particularly facilitate the formation of bimetallic frameworks by ensuring that metal ions and organic linkers effectively interact at elevated temperatures within short time frames. This method enhances the uniform incorporation of multiple metal species and can reduce the synthesis time from hours to minutes, which is advantageous for scaling up production [31]. Recently, a series of BMOFs incorporating different metal ion combinations (NiCo, NiZn, and CoZn) have been synthesized using 1,4-diazobicyclo[2.2.2]octane (DABCO) and benzene-1,4-dicarboxylate (BDC) as organic linkers via a rapid microwave-assisted thermal conversion method [70]. Remarkably, this approach enables the formation of well-crystallized BMOFs within only 12 min, demonstrating the superior efficiency and time-saving advantage of microwave-assisted synthesis. The resulting materials exhibit promising potential for oxygen evolution reactions. In a work exploring microwave-assisted solvothermal synthesis of M/Fe-MOFs (M = Ni, Mg, Sn), researchers found that the introduction of second metal ions into the MIL-88B(Fe) framework significantly altered morphology and physicochemical properties [71]. For example, incorporation of Ni²⁺ into Fe-MIL resulted in increased porosity and surface area compared with the monometallic parent structure, with corresponding improvements in photocatalytic behavior. The study underscores how solvothermal conditions combined with microwave energy influence crystal size, defect density, and surface chemistry in bimetallic frameworks.

Template-assisted synthesis is another emerging approach involving the use of templates or sacrificial supports that guide the formation of BMOF structures. This method often uses porous materials that can be filled with metal ions and linkers, creating a framework that mimics the template structure after its removal [72]. This approach can yield frameworks with unique morphologies and improved porosity, which are crucial for applications such as gas adsorption and catalysis. For example, using layered double hydroxides as templates, the synthesized two-dimensional BMOF nanosheets provides desirable properties for electrocatalysis [73].

Three-dimensional (3D) printing and related additive manufacturing techniques are increasingly being explored as advanced fabrication routes to shape and integrate MOFs into structured, device-ready architectures while maintaining their intrinsic porosity and mixed-metal chemistry. Traditional MOF powders, including complex bimetallic

variants, are challenging to process into mechanically robust forms required for electrodes and reactors; printing methods such as direct ink writing (DIW) and robocasting address this by depositing MOF-laden inks into predetermined geometries with hierarchical porosity and tunable macrostructure. For example, high-solids, pseudoplastic inks containing iron-based MOFs have been used to print 3D cellular lattices that fully integrate the MOF within a composite architecture while preserving catalytic activity in phenol hydroxylation, demonstrating how structured printing can enhance accessibility and functional performance relative to powders [74]. Although most current work has focused on monometallic frameworks, the same strategies are directly applicable to bimetallic MOFs by formulating inks that disperse mixed-metal crystals uniformly, thereby retaining compositional homogeneity after printing and drying. In foundational studies, 3D printing of MOF monoliths such as MOF-74(Ni) and UTSA-16(Co) via robocasting achieved self-supporting structures with significant CO₂ uptake, indicating that printing can preserve framework chemistry and adsorption behavior, an outcome that would be similarly desirable for bimetallic MOF variants with synergistic active sites [75]. Complementary gel-print-grow approaches, in which MOF precursor gels are printed and subsequently crystallized in situ, have been shown to produce well-formed MOF monoliths with diffractive patterns comparable to parent powders, suggesting that printing can control crystallinity as well as macro-geometry [76]. Despite most existing reports focusing on single-metal systems, recent reviews highlight 3D printing as a promising strategy to overcome rheological and structural limitations for integrating MOFs into electrochemical and separation devices, and these insights are directly translatable to the emerging arena of bimetallic MOF fabrication and applications [77].

The use of biological systems, including microorganisms or plant extracts, to synthesize BMOFs has emerged as a “green” alternative to traditional chemical methods. These biogenic approaches often employ natural reducing agents that can lead to more environmentally friendly metal reductions and complexations [46,78]. Biogenic synthesis allows for enhanced sustainability in producing BMOFs, leveraging nature for controlled and efficient synthesis. Specifically, certain bacteria can facilitate the deposition of metal ions while incorporating them into organic frameworks, thus allowing for the fabrication of unique bimetallic materials with biocompatibility and high functional diversity [79].

2.1.2. Post-synthetic modifications (PSMs)

Post-synthetic approaches involve introducing a second metal into a pre-synthesized monometallic MOF. For this purpose, a monometallic MOF is soaked in a solution containing ions of the second metal. The second metal ion then diffuses into the MOF, replacing or complementing the original metal [80,81]. This approach allows fine control through precise adjustment of the metal composition without altering the overall structure of the framework. This method is versatile because it can modify existing MOFs for targeted applications (e.g., catalysis or gas separation). However, achieving uniform incorporation of the second metal, especially in the inner regions of the MOFs, can be challenging. Furthermore, maintaining the structural integrity of MOFs throughout the modification process is another challenge. PSM is mainly used for the post-modification of MOFs to enhance or tailor their properties. These PSM strategies include metal-ion exchange, ligand exchange, covalent functionalization, and incorporation of additional components.

In post-synthetic metal-ion exchange (metalation), one metal species in the framework is partially replaced by or supplemented with a second metal introduced after synthesis. For example, studies on bimetallic Zr/Ce-MOF-808 indicate that metal exchange can enhance the stability and reactivity of the MOF compared to its single-metal counterparts [82]. The use of metal exchange is generally easy to perform and can be tuned based on the desired functional properties. This technique often targets coordinatively unsaturated metal sites within the MOF that can bond with additional metal ions [83]. For instance, in bimetallic systems, one

may introduce a second metal to form alloys or specific catalytic sites that enhance reactivity compared to pure single-metal MOFs. The careful selection of metal ions allows for creating specific electronic properties and coordination environments [84].

Ligand exchange/modification serves as another essential technique within PSM, enabling the replacement of existing organic linkers with new ones that possess different functional groups or steric environments, or altered to introduce different functionalities. This approach significantly modifies the electronic structure, hydrophobicity, or chelation capabilities of the framework [85]. For example, ligands functionalized with amines can enhance the material's coordination chemistry, promoting interactions with substrates in catalytic applications. Importantly, such modifications can occur without disrupting the MOF's overall architecture, preserving its inherent porosity. Furthermore, ligands can also be altered through post-synthetic chemical reactions, allowing extensive functionalization of the MOF [86,87]. For instance, incorporating redox-active ligands can significantly affect the electronic properties, increasing their applicability for electrocatalytic applications [88].

Several other PSM strategies are possible, including covalent modifications, non-covalent modifications, and sequential transformations using multiple synthetic strategies. Covalent PSMs enable the attachment of specific functional groups onto the MOF structure through chemical reactions that preserve the framework's integrity [89,90]. This strategy often involves utilizing reactive centers within the MOF to facilitate these attachments, potentially exposing new active sites for catalytic applications. An example includes the introduction of sulfide or nitrile groups to enhance the adsorption capacity for specific pollutants [91,92]. The versatility of covalent modifications allows for the fine-tuning of electronic and steric properties of MOFs, directly impacting their reactivity and selectivity in catalytic applications [87].

Beyond covalent approaches, non-covalent methods are essential for introducing functionalities into BMOFs. These methods primarily utilize weaker interactions, such as van der Waals forces and hydrogen bonding, to embed functional molecules or nanoparticles within the MOF structure [93]. For instance, the encapsulation of polymers into the pores of a MOF using van der Waals interactions has been shown to change the mechanical properties of the framework, enhancing its application in flexible electronics [94]. The ability to integrate non-covalent functionalities exemplifies the adaptability of PSM techniques in the engineering of bimetallic MOFs.

The sequential transformations combine multiple PSMs to achieve the desired modifications in a controlled manner [95,96]. For example, a bimetallic MOF could undergo initial metal ion exchange followed by ligand modifications, each step introducing additional functionalities that collectively enhance the overall performance of the material. This methodology provides a pathway for fine-tuning the electronic properties of hybrid frameworks, which can be crucial when optimizing them for specific reactions such as CO₂ reduction or pollutant capture [26,44].

2.2. Properties of BMOFs and their derived materials

BMOFs represent more than a compositional extension of monometallic MOFs. The introduction of a second metal center changes the local coordination environment, electronic structure, defect population, and crystallization kinetics of the framework. These changes are beneficial for different applications such as catalysis, sensing, and water treatment, as well as for electrochemical energy storage [39,44]. In monometallic MOFs, the redox response, conductivity, and ion accessibility are largely governed by one type of metal–ligand coordination environment. In contrast, BMOFs contain two chemically distinct metal centers that may differ in ionic radius, preferred coordination geometry, ligand-field strength, electronegativity, and accessible oxidation states. This creates local heterogeneity at the metal nodes and produces metal–metal electronic communication through bridging ligands, such as M–O–M' or M–N–M' motifs. As a result, the second metal can alter the d-

orbital occupancy, shift the metal-centered density of states, redistribute charge across the metal–ligand network, and change the binding strength of electrolyte ions or redox intermediates. These effects are central to SC performance because capacitance depends not only on surface area but also on the density of electrochemically accessible redox sites, electron-transfer kinetics, electrolyte wetting, ion diffusion pathways, and structural resilience during repeated charge–discharge cycles. The complementary properties of different metal centers, leading to improved electronic conductivity, enhanced stability, and tunable porosity in BMOFs are crucial for effective energy storage (Fig. 4) [97].

In pristine BMOFs, the bimetallic effect arises primarily from the intact coordination framework, with its most immediate impact being the modulation of electronic structure [98,99]. Incorporation of a heterometal into the MOF lattice introduces differences in ligand-field stabilization and metal–ligand covalency, which in turn perturb the frontier electronic states of the framework. As a result, the band gap can narrow, carrier density can increase, and overall charge transport can be enhanced [56,69]. Furthermore, when two distinct metal centers are linked via bridging ligands (e.g., M–O–M' or M–N–M'), electronic coupling between them facilitates partial charge redistribution and promotes electron hopping. This effect is particularly significant for MOFs, which typically suffer from low intrinsic conductivity. Theoretically, introducing a second metal into an existing MOF lattice alters the local electronic and geometric environment of the metal centers and the extended framework in three interrelated ways: (i) by changing the ligand-field and d-orbital occupancy of the metal nodes [100], (ii) by enabling site-specific charge redistribution and metal–metal electronic coupling [47], and (iii) by modifying defect/vacancy populations and SBU connectivity [101]. All of these together reconfigure the material's density of states and chemical reactivity. A clear example is Mn-doped Ni-MOF nanosheets, where DFT calculations showed that Mn incorporation significantly reduced the band gap of Ni-MOF and increased carrier concentration. This enhancement arises from electron transfer between Ni²⁺ and Mn²⁺ via bridging oxygen (Mn–O–Ni) [98]. This electronic rearrangement improved conductivity and enabled the NiMn-MOF electrode to deliver high areal capacity and stable hybrid-supercapacitor performance. Such a result is important because it demonstrates that the second metal does not merely provide additional redox-active sites, it changes the electronic landscape through which electrons move during fast charging and discharging. This electronic rearrangement also facilitates better redox utilization of Ni/Mn centers during rapid charge-discharge cycles. In another recent Ni/Mn-MOF electrode prepared by in situ cathodic electrodeposition, theoretical calculations similarly indicated that an optimized Ni/Mn ratio narrows the energy gap and enhances interatomic electron transfer [102]. Similar DFT-guided logic has also been extended to NiCo-MOF-74 nanoparticle arrays, where Co incorporation reduced the calculated band gap from 1.68 eV for Ni-MOF-74 to 1.46 eV for NiCo-MOF-74, indicating more favorable electronic transport in the bimetallic framework [103]. Computational analysis is particularly useful when the bimetallic framework contains conductive ligands or undergoes conversion into derivatives. In 3D bimetallic conductive MOFs based on a π -conjugated thiazole ligand, DFT analysis showed that combining Ni/Co nodes with an extended conjugated linker strengthens metal–ligand orbital hybridization. This improves electronic pathways, explaining the higher conductivity of the bimetallic framework compared with its monometallic analogues [104]. Similarly, Ag-based bimetallic MOFs containing Co or Ni have been reported to show reduced band gaps and improved SC performance, reinforcing the importance of metal-dependent electronic-structure modulation [105]. For BMOF-derived materials, the relevant descriptors shift from intact-framework band structure to interfacial charge transfer, vacancy formation, and electrolyte-ion adsorption energy. MOF-derived carbon-coated Ni–Co phosphides containing phosphorus vacancies provide a useful example [106]. The bimetallic phosphide phase, N-doped carbon coating, and P vacancies were designed to improve hydroxide-ion storage, addressing

Fig. 4. Desirable properties of BMOFs that are suitable for SC application.

the sluggish charge-transfer kinetics of transition-metal phosphides. Likewise, DFT analysis of MOF-derived Mn/Ni hydroxides showed increased electron density near the Fermi level and enhanced quantum capacitance for an optimized Mn/Ni ratio [107]. These studies clarify why pristine BMOFs and BMOF-derived electrodes should not be mechanistically treated as identical. In pristine BMOFs, ligand-mediated electronic coupling and redox-site accessibility are dominant, whereas in derived materials, vacancy chemistry, reconstructed interfaces, density of states near the Fermi level, and OH^- adsorption/desorption energetics play more important roles.

Similarly, Ni–Co [40], Co–Fe [108], and Zn–Co [100] BMOFs often show improved electrochemical behavior because the secondary metal tunes the local redox environment, stabilizes mixed-valence states, and increases the density of accessible electroactive centers. Similar electronic principles have been observed in other bimetallic MOF systems outside SCs. For example, atomically dispersed Ru in Ni-BDC was shown by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS), charge-density analysis, and density-of-states calculations to withdraw electron density from Ni, shift the Ni d-band center, and optimize intermediate adsorption [101]. Although this example was not reported for SCs, it demonstrates how heterometal incorporation can redistribute charge and tune metal-centered electronic states. These effects are relevant to BMOF-based SC electrodes because similar electronic modulation can enhance charge-transfer kinetics, redox-site utilization, and electrolyte-ion interaction at active metal centers. These effects have been mapped experimentally and computationally across families of bimetallic frameworks [47]. Operando and in situ studies on NiCo carbonate hydroxide electrodes further highlight the importance of tracking structural changes under working conditions [109]. During cycling, the working electrode reconstructed into oxygen-vacancy-rich NiCo layered double hydroxide, and theoretical modelling identified unsaturated Co sites as favorable redox centers. Although this system is not a pristine BMOF example, it is highly relevant to BMOF-derived oxides/hydroxides because many MOF-derived Ni/Co, Ni/Fe, or Co/Fe phases likely undergo similar electrolyte-induced reconstruction. Related in situ studies on cobalt hydroxide systems have also shown that the active charge-storage phase may differ from the initially synthesized material [110]. Therefore, the true electroactive surface of BMOF-derived electrodes should be identified under operating conditions rather than inferred only from pristine-state characterization. In other reports, solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) combined with operando electrochemical quartz crystal

microbalance (EQCM) revealed cation-dominated charge storage in $\text{Ni}_3(\text{HITP})_2$ MOF [111]. Operando small-angle X-ray scattering further showed selective immobilization of TFSI^- anions near $\text{Ni}_3(\text{HITP})_2$ MOF pore walls, leading to Na^+ -dominated charge compensation. Although these examples are not bimetallic, they are valuable mechanistic precedents as they show that MOF pores cannot be treated as inert voids, because specific ion–framework interactions determine whether charge storage occurs by ion adsorption, desolvation, intercalation, or surface redox. In this context, applying similar operando approaches to BMOFs would clarify the role of each metal center during capacitive operation. Such studies would help determine whether both metals actively participate in charge compensation or whether one primarily modulates the local electrostatic environment, ion solvation, and transport pathways.

Another advantage of BMOFs over monometallic MOFs is that their physical properties can be tailored by tuning the metal/ligand ratios, linker chemistry, and synthesis conditions [98,112]. Although pristine BMOFs also suffer from limited electronic conductivity, the incorporation of conductive agents such as carbon nanotubes or graphene into BMOFs can improve their conductivity and mechanical strength [113,114]. Additionally, the integration of BMOFs with other functional materials such as MXenes and LDHs is beneficial for tuning the interfacial chemistry at the electrode/electrolyte interface [40,115,116]. These composite materials exhibit improved charge transport properties, which are essential for fast charging cycles. The bimetallic nature of these frameworks introduces the potential for co-catalytic activities which can be utilized in tandem processes, such as those involved in hybrid devices that combine SCs with batteries.

The second major effect is redox diversification. In pristine BMOFs, the two metal centers can provide complementary redox couples, such as $\text{Ni}^{2+}/\text{Ni}^{3+}$, $\text{Co}^{2+}/\text{Co}^{3+}$, $\text{Mn}^{2+}/\text{Mn}^{3+}/\text{Mn}^{4+}$, or $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$, depending on the metal composition, electrolyte, and operating potential window. The coexistence of these redox centers broadens the range of accessible Faradaic reactions and can increase charge storage capacity relative to monometallic analogues. This redox versatility enables BMOFs to engage in multiple electron-transfer processes, illustrating their potential for substantial energy storage and high-power density in SC applications [117,118]. However, the benefit is not automatic. A poorly chosen metal ratio may block pores, distort the framework, or introduce electronically isolated sites. Therefore, the bimetallic ratio must be optimized so that the added metal increases redox-site utilization without compromising crystallinity, conductivity, or electrolyte

accessibility. Recent NiMn-MOF nanosheet electrodes illustrate this balance as their layered architecture and mixed Ni/Mn redox chemistry promoted Faradaic-dominated intercalation pseudocapacitance [119]. In this process, electrolyte ions enter the open framework and participate in rapid, reversible redox reactions rather than being restricted to surface adsorption. This example connects bimetallic chemistry directly to a supercapacitor-relevant mechanism i.e., orbital/redox tuning combined with open ion channels gives faster charge compensation and higher capacitance.

Bimetallic incorporation also strongly affects defect chemistry and pore hierarchy, both of which are critical for SC performance [44,120]. Because the two metal ions usually have different metal–ligand bond strengths, hydrolysis tendencies, coordination numbers, and nucleation rates, their simultaneous incorporation can generate missing-linker defects, unsaturated metal sites, lattice strain, and non-uniform growth domains. These features can be beneficial when controlled. Defects expose additional metal sites, increase electrolyte-accessible surface area, and create local electrostatic environments that favor ion adsorption. At the same time, excessive defects can destabilize the framework and accelerate dissolution under cycling. Thus, defect chemistry in BMOFs should be understood as a double-edged design variable. Although some mechanistic studies on BMOFs have been reported in electrocatalysis, adsorption, or environmental remediation rather than directly in SCs, they provide useful structure-property principles for designing BMOF-based SC electrodes. For example, studies on heterometallic imidazolate frameworks have shown that ligand vacancies and Co–Zn heterometallic coordination can steer d-orbital occupancy and generate hierarchical pores that deliver excellent electrocatalytic activity [100]. In other reports, bimetallic frameworks have shown strong potential in cooperative catalysis, pollutant degradation, and adsorption processes, benefiting from tunable pore hierarchy and defect chemistry [121–123]. Finally, various reviews and perspectives show that bimetallic motifs not only tune catalytic and adsorption energetics via electronic effects but also influence mechanical stability, defect chemistry and electron-phonon coupling [26,124]. For instance, the synergistic effect of different metals demonstrated the improved catalytic performance, especially in electrocatalytic reactions such as oxygen evolution and CO₂ reduction [39,125–127]. Apart from the catalytic activity, the incorporation of multiple metal ions with a more uniform distribution in the framework enhances the material's overall stability and reactivity [56,128]. The resulting materials often exhibit excellent mechanical properties and durability, making them suitable for demanding environments [129]. The same concept is mechanistically relevant for SCs because the same combination of open metal sites, hierarchical pores, and tuned metal d-states can improve electrolyte penetration, reduce ion-diffusion resistance, and increase the number of redox-active sites accessible at high current density. Therefore, the influence of bimetallicity on pore hierarchy and ion transport is particularly important for SCs [84,85]. Micropores provide high surface area, but electrolyte ions may be partially solvated and kinetically restricted within narrow channels. Mesopores and macropores, by contrast, act as ion-buffering and transport reservoirs. BMOFs can integrate these length scales when mixed-metal crystallization produces nanosheets, hollow particles, intergrown domains, or defect-expanded channels. Furthermore, the intrinsic porosity of BMOFs, which can be precisely tuned during synthesis, contributes to a hierarchical structure that enhances ion transport and diffusion. This tunability is especially advantageous in optimizing charge storage pathways, thus improving the overall electrochemical performance of SCs. The incorporation of bimetallic centers often results in stronger interactions within the framework, leading to enhanced structural integrity under repeated cycling conditions typically experienced in SC operations. In SC electrodes, this hierarchical porosity reduces the distance for electrolyte-ion diffusion, improves wetting, and enables deeper utilization of internal redox sites. For example, 2D NiCo-MOF/MXene heterostructures combine redox-active Ni/Co sites with a conductive MXene network and open lamellar

diffusion pathways [40]. The NiCo-MOF/MXene electrode displayed markedly higher capacitance than pristine NiCo-MOF, showing that bimetallic redox chemistry alone is insufficient unless coupled with conductive and ion-accessible architecture.

BMOFs can also serve as effective precursors for derived materials. Post-synthesis treatments, such as pyrolysis can yield carbon-based materials that retain the morphology or porosity of the parent MOF while providing additional electrical conductivity and chemical stability, which is beneficial for energy storage applications [130]. However, the role of bimetallicity differs in BMOF-derived materials. During thermal, chemical, or electrochemical conversion, the pristine coordination framework is partly or completely transformed into oxides, hydroxides, chalcogenides, phosphides, or carbon-supported metal compounds. In this case, the original BMOF acts as a chemically programmed precursor rather than the final active framework. The advantages of the bimetallic precursor are retained in several ways. First, the two metals are often distributed homogeneously at the molecular or nanoscale in the parent MOF, which suppresses large-scale phase segregation during conversion and favors the formation of mixed-metal compounds or intimate heterointerfaces. Second, decomposition of the organic linker can generate conductive carbon, while the metal nodes convert into electrochemically active nanoparticles, nanosheets, or hollow structures. Third, differences in metal diffusion rates and chalcogenation/phosphidation/oxidation kinetics can induce Kirkendall voids, hierarchical porosity, and abundant vacancies. Therefore, in BMOF-derived materials, bimetallicity influences SC behavior less through the original metal–ligand framework and more through the formation of conductive heterostructures, defect-rich interfaces, and mechanically robust porous architectures. For example, bimetallic Ni–Co oxides derived from MOFs exhibit improved conductivity as compared to their monometallic counterparts, that is necessary for higher charge-discharge rates and utilization of redox processes [131]. Therefore, BMOF-derived oxides, hydroxides, chalcogenides, and phosphides typically exhibit higher electrical conductivity and structural robustness than pristine MOFs, while retaining the compositional uniformity and morphology inherited from the parent framework. A review on bimetallic MOFs and their derivatives emphasized that BMOFs can act as templates for nanomaterials with controlled size, composition, and structure, while their derivatives often show improved conductivity, stability, and exposed active sites for electrochemical energy storage and conversion [26]. This distinction is essential for SCs as pristine BMOFs are attractive because of their tunable redox-active coordination environments, but their conductivity and stability can be limited. By contrast, BMOF-derived materials, often sacrifice long-range crystallinity but gain conductive phases, heterointerfaces, vacancies, and mechanically resilient architectures that favor high-rate pseudocapacitance. Several other examples illustrate this difference. For instance, in oxygen-vacancy-rich CoFe-MOF grown on carbon cloth, the optimized Co/Fe combination and abundant oxygen vacancies increased active-site utilization, improved conductivity, and produced excellent cycling stability in a flexible asymmetric SC [108]. Here, the bimetallic effect is not simply the sum of Co and Fe redox activity; Fe modifies the Co-centered electronic environment, while oxygen vacancies create additional charge-compensation sites and facilitate electrolyte access. Likewise, NiCo₂S₄–Ni₉S₈–C double-layered yolk–shell microspheres derived from a bimetallic MOF benefit from NiCo₂S₄/Ni₉S₈ heterointerfaces and a porous carbon-containing yolk–shell architecture [132]. In such materials, the parent BMOF determines metal distribution and morphology, while the conversion step generates sulfide heterointerfaces and conductive carbon that enhance electron transport, buffer volume changes, and shorten ion-diffusion pathways. These examples show why BMOF-derived materials are often more suitable than pristine BMOFs for high-power or long-cycle SC operation. Furthermore, the design of BMOFs allows for the incorporation and tailored distribution of functional groups that can participate in electrochemical reactions. This functionalization increases the number of active sites available and

may enhance the selectivity of the charge storage processes, thus improving energy efficiency and reducing the self-discharge rates, a critical factor for practical applications of SCs [133].

Overall, the key distinction between pristine BMOFs and BMOF-derived materials lies in how bimetallicity is expressed. In pristine BMOFs, the second metal tunes the intact coordination framework through ligand-field effects, charge redistribution, mixed-valence redox chemistry, and defect-controlled pore accessibility. In BMOF-derived materials, the second metal guides phase evolution, heterointerface formation, vacancy generation, carbon incorporation, and hierarchical morphology during conversion. Both routes can enhance SC performance, but they address different limitations. Pristine BMOFs offer atomic-level redox tunability and well-defined porosity, whereas derived materials provide higher conductivity, stronger structural tolerance, and richer interfacial pseudocapacitance. Future BMOF electrode design should therefore move beyond empirical metal mixing and adopt a more rational selection of metal pairs. Key criteria should include complementary redox potentials, metal–ligand bond strengths, electronic coupling, conversion behavior, and ability to generate stable ion/electron transport networks under realistic SC operating conditions.

2.3. Hierarchical structures of BMOFs

The hierarchical structures of BMOFs may be categorized into porous hierarchical structures, architectural hierarchical structures, and compositional hierarchical structures (Fig. 5). Porous hierarchical structures commonly comprise micro-, meso-, and macropores, which are important for facilitating ion transport and accessibility to active sites during charge-discharge cycles. Furthermore, the hierarchical assembly of MOF crystallites into superstructures enhances packing density and enables the creation of multifunctional architectures for applications such as gas capture, transport, and catalysis [50,134–138]. The hierarchical structures define BMOFs with distinct morphologies or dimensionalities including zero-dimensional (0D), one-dimensional (1D), two-dimensional (2D), and three-dimensional (3D) offering different electrochemical performances. Finally, the compositional hierarchical structures are related to the arrangement of varying components in a single framework yielding synergistic contributions in energy storage.

However, the question arises as to how the presence of two or more

metals affects the hierarchical structure of the framework. Briefly, incorporation of a second metal into a MOF lattice perturbs framework architecture in a systematic, atomically traceable manner that often produces hierarchical pore structures and enhances *meso*–/*microporosity*. This effect arises from three principal, interlinked mechanisms. First, heterometal substitution alters the coordination geometry and preferred SBU connectivity because different cations possess distinct ionic radii, preferred coordination numbers, and ligand-field strengths. These differences change bond angles and linker dispositions during nucleation and growth, producing altered crystal habits and interparticle packing that manifest as enlarged or interconnected pores. Evidence for this SBU-level origin is seen in heterometal imidazolate frameworks where Co↔Zn incorporation, together with deliberately introduced ligand vacancies, reconfigures local connectivity and generates hierarchical pore networks [100]. Second, mixed-metal chemistry promotes controlled defect formation and selective site instability. A labile metal (or one more prone to hydrolysis or partial leaching under synthesis/activation conditions) can act as a sacrificial progen or create missing linker/cluster defects that enlarge micropores into mesopores. Such defect-mediated pore engineering has been demonstrated in Fe–Mn and other bimetallic BTC systems, which show significantly increased mesopore volume and hierarchical architectures formed in one-pot syntheses [139,140]. Third, electronic and kinetic effects at the atomic scale influence pore formation and morphology. Specifically, differences in metal–ligand bond strength and activation barriers can create spatially heterogeneous nucleation rates and growth fronts. These effects produce core–shell, domain-segregated, or intergrown morphologies with multiscale porosity. Non-equilibrium synthesis routes (e.g., flame aerosol or rapid solvothermal conversion) further lock in such mixed-metal topologies even when thermodynamics would favor segregation [55].

Although hierarchical BMOF architectures are often described in terms of their final morphology, their formation is governed by a relatively small set of synthesis variables that control nucleation, crystal-growth direction, defect formation, and particle assembly (Table 1) [141]. Among these variables, pH is one of the most decisive parameters because it regulates ligand deprotonation, metal hydrolysis, and the relative rate of nucleation versus crystal growth [142]. At low pH, protonated carboxylate or azolate ligands coordinate more slowly, often favoring fewer nuclei and larger or more crystalline particles. At higher

Fig. 5. Hierarchical structures of BMOFs.

Table 1
Different synthesis conditions directly related to hierarchical outcomes.

Synthesis parameter(s)	Primary chemical role	Likely hierarchical outcome	Relevance to SCs
pH / base concentration	Controls ligand deprotonation and metal hydrolysis	Nanosheets, small particles, defect-rich structures, or hydroxide impurities if excessive	Determines redox-site exposure, ion access, and framework stability
Solvent polarity/ coordinating ability	Controls precursor solubility, diffusion, ligand deprotonation, and facet growth	Rods, hydrangea-like aggregates, spherulites, porous microspheres	Regulates electrolyte wetting and ion-diffusion length
Ligand geometry/ denticity	Determines framework connectivity and growth dimensionality	1D rods, 2D sheets, 3D cages, layer-channel structures	Controls ion channels and redox-site accessibility
Ligand steric hindrance	Slows or redirects growth at specific facets/ interfaces	Ultrathin sheets, shell/domain structures, defect-opened pores	Improves active-site exposure and prevents dense aggregation
Metal-ion ratio	Tunes redox-site density and coordination kinetics	Core-shell, gradient, or phase-segregated structures	Balances redox activity with ion/electron transport
Temperature/time	Controls nucleation, ripening, and self-assembly	Dense crystals, hollow/flower-like particles, tubes, nanospheres	Affects crystallinity, mechanical robustness, and rate capability
Modulators/surfactants/ templates	Cap facets, compete with linkers, guide mesoscale assembly	Mesopores, hollow particles, nanosheets, ordered macrochannels	Enables electrolyte reservoirs and fast ion highways

pH, rapid ligand deprotonation and metal–ligand complexation can generate a high density of nuclei, smaller particles, nanosheets, or defect-rich structures. However, excessive alkalinity may also promote metal hydroxide formation or framework disorder. Coordination-modulation studies have shown that acidic or basic modulators can alter particle size, morphology, porosity, and defectivity by competing with framework linkers during SBU formation and crystal growth [143]. For example, sodium acetate or amine-type modulators can increase reaction pH and redirect MOF growth, while carboxylic-acid modulators can selectively cap specific crystal faces and suppress growth along particular directions. This is highly relevant for BMOF-based SC electrodes because pH-controlled nanosheets, hollow particles, or mesoporous aggregates can shorten ion-diffusion distances and expose more metal redox-active sites, whereas uncontrolled over-deprotonation may introduce unstable defects that accelerate structural degradation during cycling.

Solvent polarity, coordinating ability, and decomposition behavior also strongly influence hierarchical structure formation. Solvents are not inert media in MOF synthesis. They determine precursor solubility, ligand deprotonation, metal-ion stabilization, viscosity, diffusion rate, and sometimes act as weak coordinating agents or decomposition modulators. In polar aprotic solvents such as DMF, stronger solvation and gradual ligand deprotonation can promote anisotropic or rough hierarchical growth, whereas protic solvents such as methanol or ethanol can lead to faster precipitation or different aggregation pathways depending on the ligand and metal salt. Solvent-controlled Ni/Co-MOF studies using 3,5-diaminobenzoic acid showed a clear morphology evolution from smooth rod-like structures to hydrangea-like architectures as the solvent changed from alcohols to DMF, and the DMF-derived porous morphology giving superior capacitive behavior [144]. Related work on solvent-regulated Ni-MOF also shows that ethanol, methanol, and DMF can drive rod-like, smooth hydrangea-like, and rough hydrangea-like morphologies, respectively [145]. These examples demonstrate that solvent choice affects not only crystallinity but also the secondary mesoscopic assembly that determines electrolyte wetting, pore accessibility, and rate capability in SC electrodes.

The organic linker controls hierarchy through denticity, geometry, rigidity, electronic character, and steric demand. Linear dicarboxylate linkers often favor rod-like or layered growth. In contrast, trigonal linkers such as BTC can promote multidirectional branching or microsphere formation, while azolate ligands often produce dense zeolitic networks with well-defined polyhedral morphologies [146]. Mixed-linker strategies add another level of control because one ligand may act as the main framework-forming linker, while another may slow lateral growth, introduce defects, or tune interlayer stacking. Sterically bulky linkers or mixed linkers can suppress growth along specific directions by imposing spatial constraints at the crystal surface or at MOF-on-MOF interfaces [147]. For example, studies on sterically hindered MOF-on-MOF systems show that bulky linkers weaken or redirect

interfacial connections. Recent work on stratified MOFs demonstrates that ligand steric demand can control ligand exchange and domain growth [148]. These principles are directly transferable to BMOFs. Bulky or asymmetric ligands can slow dense crystal growth, and help preserve open channels. They can also promote shell/domain structures in which ion-accessible outer layers and redox-rich inner domains are spatially organized. In the context of SCs, such ligand-directed anisotropic growth is especially useful for producing ultrathin nanosheets, open flower-like structures, or intergrown domains that improve active-site exposure and reduce ion-transport resistance.

Furthermore, beyond the use of pure BMOF structures, they can serve as templates or sacrificial agents to produce derived nanostructures with high surface area and well-defined porosity, improving charge storage and long-term cycling stability in SCs [31,149]. The concept behind sacrificial templating involves utilizing a scaffold that is subsequently removed to create a desired porous structure in the final material. The mechanisms of sacrificial templating involve strategic manipulation of various compounds to create precisely controlled environments, such as using MOFs that can be thermally or chemically processed to yield porous structures when the template is eliminated. Literature studies indicate that MOFs are especially favorable as they inherently possess tunable porosity, large surface areas, and a framework designed to accommodate multiple active sites for bimetallic complexes [56,97]. Apart from using BMOFs as templates to derive other products, template-assisted synthesis can be applied during BMOF formation to tune the porosity in the MOF structure. These template-assisted synthesis methods can be categorized into hard and soft templating. Hard templates, which include materials like silica or carbon, are used to develop the desired pore architectures during the formation of BMOFs. The subsequent removal of the template results in intricate porous networks that are beneficial for applications in energy storage [150]. Additionally, the use of soft templates, such as surfactants, can facilitate the creation of unique morphological structures that enhance performance metrics [151,152]. The versatility of these templating strategies is a key for achieving tailored pore size distributions, which is instrumental in maximizing surface areas relevant for SC applications [153,154].

By tuning nucleation kinetics and crystallization conditions, diverse BMOF morphologies with tailored pore sizes and chemical environments can be expected. Hierarchically porous MOF-74 tubular superstructures have been synthesized in a one-pot process. It involved self-healing fusion of tubes at 85 °C which produced a unified architecture with aligned micro- and macropores [155]. Solvent choice, such as N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) or N,N-diethylformamide (DEF), significantly affects the assembly due to their differing decomposition rates, enabling the formation of spherulite superstructures with unique optical properties and radial nanofibril organization [156]. These spherulites deviate from traditional crystallization due to small-angle branching. Further, by using tertiary MOF-74 spherulites as seeds, quaternary

heterostructures with dendritic (MOF-74-II) and spherulitic (MOF-74-III) components were synthesized, showcasing a rare tree-like morphology [157]. Such multilevel MOF architectures offer abundant electroactive sites, interconnected ion/electron transport pathways, and enhanced structural stability. They collectively facilitate charge transfer, efficient diffusion of ions, and superior cycling stability, which are key features for achieving high-performance SCs.

An important feature of compositional hierarchical structures in MOFs is the nature of the interfaces between their structural modules. In MOF-on-MOF systems with matched lattices, precise molecular-level interfaces can form, as seen in MOF-5-NH₂@MOF-5 [158] and HKUST-1@MOF-5 [159] core-shell structures, where epitaxial growth or metal-linker coordination ensures seamless integration. In contrast, MOF-on-MOF structures with mismatched lattices can form interfaces through three main mechanisms: defect-mediated connections, polymer mediation, or coordination of polymer bridges. For example, MOF@COF composites produced via spray-drying exhibit interfacial defects and porosity due to rapid crystallization [160]. These strategies are highly beneficial for enhancing efficient charge and ion transport, electrolyte accessibility and exposure of electrochemically active sites. However, slower crystallization can lead to the formation of coordination linkages with minimal mesoscopic defects [161]. Polymers also serve as effective connectors between structurally diverse MOFs, enabling the integration of components with differing lattice structures and morphologies, providing mechanical integrity and structural stability during repeated charging-discharging [162].

3. BMOFs, their derived materials and hybrids for SCs

In the current section, we discuss various types of BMOFs and BMOF-derived materials, along with their corresponding hybrids, emphasizing their applicability for SC applications. This section highlights the synthetic methodologies employed for obtaining these materials and examines how the different factors such as the bimetal composition, choice of ligands, solvent, and morphology influence their physicochemical properties and consequently electrochemical performance. Special emphasis has been given on understanding how these parameters affect key properties, including electrical conductivity, ion diffusion pathways, redox activity, and structural stability, which collectively govern the overall performance of SCs. Furthermore, this section discusses the need for constructing heterostructures of BMOFs and their derived materials with advanced functional materials to achieve synergistic effects that contribute to the enhancement of charge storage capabilities and cycling stability.

3.1. BMOFs and their composites

BMOFs are used in SC applications in two main ways: (i) directly as electrode materials or combined with other functional materials to leverage synergistic effects and improve electrochemical performance; and (ii) as sacrificial templates or precursors for deriving functional materials (e.g., oxides, hydroxides, chalcogenides (S, Se, Te), and phosphides) that can be further integrated into composites to enhance electrochemical properties. This section provides a comprehensive discussion on the direct application of BMOFs as electrode materials and the development of BMOF-based composites with advanced functional materials, emphasizing their role in enhancing specific capacitance, rate capability, and the cycling stability of SCs.

Wei and co-workers reported Mn-doped Ni-MOF (NiMn-MOF) nanosheets grown on nickel foam (NF) to construct a binder-free electrode for SC [98]. The binder-free growth of NiMn-MOF nanosheets on Ni foam ensures direct electrical contact and efficient charge transport, minimizing interfacial resistance and thereby enhancing the overall SC performance. The optimum molar ratio of Ni to Mn (7:3) was found to be crucial for forming O-bridged NiMn bimetallic centers via polarity-induced solvothermal method, which effectively modulates the

electrochemical performance of the BMOF. The as-obtained Ni_{0.7}Mn_{0.3}-MOF electrode delivers an impressive specific capacity of 1.89 mAh/cm² at a current density of 1 mA/cm². Furthermore, the asymmetric SC (ASC) assembled using Ni_{0.7}Mn_{0.3}-MOF and activated carbon (AC) (Ni_{0.7}Mn_{0.3}-MOF//AC) achieves a high energy density of 67.5 Wh/kg at a power density of 0.0849 kW/kg, along with excellent cycling stability retaining 94% of its capacitance after 10,000 cycles.

Binder-free growth of BMOFs has been achieved not only on conductive Ni foam but also on flexible carbon cloth (CC) substrate, enabling direct use of the grown BMOF as an electrode without additional binders and conductive additives. Recently, CoFe BMOF was synthesized in situ on CC (CoFeMOF@CC) using a facile hydrothermal approach and heat treatment, effectively combining synergistic benefits of Fe and Co bimetallic active metal centers [108] (Fig. 6a). The obtained bimetallic CoFeMOF@CC is enriched in oxygen vacancies and consists of ultrasmall particles. The electrochemical measurements of O_v-CoFe-MOF@CC electrode are shown in Fig. 6b-d. Cyclic voltammetry (CV) curves of O_v-CoFe-MOF@CC electrode displayed a pair of redox peaks at around 0.5 V corresponding to Co²⁺/Co³⁺ (Fig. 6b). Leveraging the optimal combination of bimetallic active metal centers (i.e., Fe and Co) and abundant oxygen vacancies, the O_v-CoFe-MOF@CC electrode achieved a high areal capacitance of 56.94 mF/cm² at 0.5 mA/cm² with a superior cycling stability of 99.67% after 30,000 cycles (Fig. 6c and d). Furthermore, when the hybrid device was assembled by using O_v-CoFe-MOF@CC as a positive electrode and nano-porous carbon material (NCM) on CC (NCM@CC) as a negative electrode, the voltage window could be extended up to 1.2 V. The ASC device exhibited a high energy density of 27.4 mWh/cm² and a power density of 4800 mW/cm², making it viable for energy storage devices.

The organic linkers play a key role in the synthesis of BMOFs by governing the framework structure, porosity, and metal coordination environment. Li et al., [112] used L-malic acid and 4,4'-bipyridine as the organic linkers and Ni and Co as bimetallic centers to synthesize Ni_nCo_m BMOFs with a layer-and-channel structure. The coordination of organic linkers with Ni and Co metal centers promotes the formation of layer-and-channel structure, which significantly enhances ion diffusion and charge transfer throughout the framework. Benefitting from these advantages, Ni_nCo_mMOF exhibited a specific capacitance of 1333 F/g at 2 A/g in 1 M KOH aqueous electrolyte. The ASC device delivered an energy density of 28 Wh/kg at 444 W/kg. The specific capacitance of NiCo BMOF electrode material was boosted (1640 F/g at 1 A/g) when synthesized by using the large and intricate hetero-organic framework composed of imidazole (Im), dimethylformamide (DMF), and benzene-1,3,5-tricarboxylic acid (BTC) organic linkers, with an optimized Ni:Co ratio of 1:2 (Btc-Im-DMF-Ni₁/Co₂) [163].

Beyond bimetallic MOFs, multimetallic MOFs containing three metal centers have also been explored as electrode materials for SC applications [164,165]. Yang et al., [165] reported NiCoMn trimetallic MOF with flower-like hierarchical microspheres. The synthesis was carried out through a solvothermal route, where the reaction duration (24 h to 48 h) was optimized to regulate the morphology and structural evolution of the framework. The NiCoMn MOF prepared with a reaction time of 48 h (MOF-48) delivered the highest specific capacitance of 1905 F/g compared with MOF-24 (790 F/g) and MOF-36 (914.8 F/g) at 1 A/g. An ASC device was assembled which delivered the energy density of 61.52 Wh/kg at a power density of 6945.4 W/kg, with the capacitance retention of 97% after 15,000 cycles.

In addition to strategies such as optimizing the molar ratio of metal centers and tailoring the organic linkers, efforts are also focused on growing BMOFs on conductive substrates, and tuning the redox activity of active metal centers, for enhancing the electrochemical performance. The BMOF-based hybrids that incorporate conductive functional supports such as reduced graphene oxide (rGO), carbon nanotubes (CNTs), and MXenes, provide redox-active heterointerfaces that combine the intrinsic pseudocapacitive activity of BMOFs with improved electrical conductivity, electrolyte accessibility, ion-transport pathways, charge-

Fig. 6. (a) Schematic illustration for the formation of O_v -CoFe-MOF@CC. Electrochemical measurements of O_v -CoFe-MOF@CC electrode in three-electrode set up using 2 M H_2SO_4 electrolyte, (b) CV curves of O_v -CoFe-MOF@CC at different scan rates, (c) galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) curves at different current densities, (d) cycling stability test at a current density of 3 mA/cm². (Reproduced with permission [108] Copyright 2024, Elsevier).

transfer kinetics, and structural stability, thereby improving overall electrochemical performance during repeated charging/discharging cycles.

Safari and colleagues [166] evaluated rGO modified CoFe-BMOF composites with different rGO contents (3–5%) for SC application. The growth of rGO decorated CoFe-BMOF was carried out on NF through an ultrasonic-assisted solvothermal method. The incorporation of 3% rGO resulted in the highest BET surface area of 149 m²/g compared with 5% rGO@CoFe-MOF (112 m²/g) and pristine CoFe-MOF (52 m²/g). The GCD curves recorded for 3% rGO@CoFe-MOF/NF at 0.5 A/g exhibited specific capacitance of 2069.1 F/g which is 64.5% higher compared with pristine CoFe-MOF. An ASC device was assembled using 3% rGO@CoFe-MOF/NF as positive and activated carbon on NF (AC@NF) as negative

electrodes, which delivers an outstanding energy density of 75.8 Wh/kg at 0.7 kW/kg in 3 M KOH aqueous electrolyte.

Heteroatom-doped graphene supports have been employed in BMOF hybrids, owing to their enhanced electrical conductivity, defect rich structure, and additional active sites. For instance, Rajpurohit and co-workers [167] fabricated a copper-iron 1,3,5-benzenetricarboxylic acid (CuFeBTC)-based BMOF on S-doped graphene (CuFeBTC/S-GNS) using a solvochemical method. As a result, CuFeBTC/S-GNS electrode material delivered the specific capacitance of 1164.3 F/g at 0.5 A/g in 1 M Na₂SO₄ electrolyte. The symmetric SC constructed using this material in 1 M Na₂SO₄ achieved an exceptional energy density of 96.57 Wh/kg at a power density of 1.595 kW/kg with the operational voltage of 1.8 V. Furthermore, the device retained 92.5% of its initial capacitance after

10,000 cycles, demonstrating its long-term cycling stability. In this hybrid, S-GNS improved electrical conductivity and interfacial accessibility, while the porous CuFeBTC framework provides abundant redox-active sites.

Beyond the commonly used transition metals like Ni, Mn, Co, Fe, and Cu, less conventional metal combinations such as Na and Zn have also been explored for BMOF-based SCs [168]. Rajak and coworkers [168] reported a combination of the bimetallic 2D layered Na/Zn-MOF with rGO through an ultrasonication method to create a hybrid heterostructure Na/Zn-MOF/rGO. The Na/Zn-MOF, synthesized with a slow diffusion method using Na^+ and Zn^{2+} ions in a 2:1 ratio, displayed octahedral and trigonal bipyramidal geometries in its structural framework. The π -interactions between adjacent 2D layers formed a supramolecular 3D framework. The hybrid exhibited a significant specific capacitance of 435.2 F/g at 1.6 A/g without employing any binders and showed no capacity loss after 4000 cycles, indicating the benefit of coupling the layered MOF framework with conductive rGO.

Recently, a simple and cost-effective approach, i.e., laser ablation synthesis in solution (LASiS) has been adopted to fabricate ZnCo BMOF based hybrid integrated with rGO [169]. The resulting ZnCo-BMOF-rGO hybrid nanocomposite (HNC) exhibited enhanced charge-transfer kinetics, mainly owing to amide linkages that promote π -conjugated structures. In this LASiS route, metal precursors, KOH, GO, and 2-methylimidazole linker solution was transferred into LASiS reactor cell. A Zn pellet was placed in the LASiS reactor cell and was ablated using a pulsed Nd:YAG laser for 10 min to obtain ZnCo-BMOF-GO HNCs, subsequently converted into ZnCo-BMOF-rGO HNCs by vacuum heating. The as-obtained ZnCo-BMOF-rGO achieved a high specific capacitance of 1092 F/g at 1 A/g in 0.5 M Na_2SO_4 solution. Furthermore, the BMOF-rGO composites have been effectively formulated into active layer ink and utilized for fabricating high-performance 3D-printed SCs through sequential inkjet printing.

In addition to 2D graphene-based materials (discussed above), 1D CNTs have also been commonly integrated with BMOFs to construct conductive hybrid electrodes. For example, Han and coworkers [170] fabricated Mn/Ni-MOF@MWCNTs hybrids by growing Mn/Ni-BMOFs on MWCNTs. Different proportions of Mn and Ni metals were used in the synthesis of Mn/Ni BMOFs, and an increased Ni content led to the formation of thinner lamellae structure. The MWCNT network preserved the BMOF morphology and provided continuous conductive pathways for the charge transfer. As a result, a high specific capacitance of 793.6 F/g was achieved at 1 A/g in 1 M LiOH aqueous solution, with a capacitance retention of 74.92% after 1000 cycles at 1 A/g.

Functionalized CNTs have also been employed to improve dispersibility within the BMOF matrix and facilitate stronger interfacial interactions with BMOFs through surface functional groups such as -COOH, -NH₂, -OH [171–173]. Recently, Choudhury and colleagues [173] reported the hybrid electrode based on hexyl-aminated CNTs (HA-CNTs), which offer excellent electrical conductivity and abundant surface functionalities, and porous Mn–Ni (3-hydroxypyridine-2-carboxylic acid) (Mn-Ni(3-HPCA) MOF/HA-CNT). The HA-CNTs served as nucleation sites to promote the uniform growth of MOF crystals leading to the formation of core-shell structure of the hybrid material. SEM and TEM images revealed the complete coverage of CNTs with Mn-Ni(3-HPCA) MOFs, forming the entangled network of Mn-Ni(3-HPCA) MOF/HA-CNT hybrid (Fig. 7a–c). The Mn-Ni(3-HPCA) MOF/HA-CNT electrode material was tested in both basic (3 M KOH) and neutral (1 M Na_2SO_4) in three-electrode system. The specific capacitance was higher in 3 M KOH (673.3 F/g at 0.25 A/g) than in 1 M Na_2SO_4 (514.4 F/g at 0.25 A/g). In 3 M KOH electrolyte, the rate capability was measured to be 73.2% at 10 A/g while it remained only 55% in 1 M Na_2SO_4 . This was attributed to the larger hydrated size of Na^+ , which restricts the intercalation/deintercalation more than hydrated K^+ ions. Furthermore, the ASC device was assembled using Mn-Ni(3-HPCA) MOF/HA-CNT as the positive and XGnP as the negative electrodes, with a KOH-loaded poly(acrylonitrile-co-1-vinylimidazole) gel electrolyte. The CV curves of the

ASC device showed more pronounced redox peaks as the potential window expands to 1.7 V (Fig. 7d and e). The ASC device delivered the specific capacitance of 287.6 F/g at 0.3 A/g, retaining 76.7% capacitance retention when the current density increased to 10 A/g (Fig. 7f–h). The ASC device achieved the maximum energy density of 67.9 Wh/kg at a power density of 0.3 kW/kg and retained as high as 47.3 Wh/kg at a high-power density of 10 kW/kg, along with a capacitance retention of 87.1% after 10,000 cycles (Fig. 7i). The practical applicability of the ASC device was demonstrated by lighting an LED (Fig. 7j).

In recent studies, one-dimensional (1D) porous CNFs (PCNFs), have also been used for the seamless integration with BMOFs [174]. PCNFs have been used as scaffold for BMOF growth, enabling freestanding electrodes with reduced inactive mass in the electrode and improved interfacial contact. Jeong and colleagues [174] synthesized NiCo MOFs on surface-engineered CNFs (NiCo CNFs) embedded with metallic nanoparticles (Ni and Co) using a hydrothermal method, resulting in a NiCo MOF@NiCo CNF composite. The metallic species in the CNFs acted as nucleation sites, promoting the uniform growth of NiCo MOF and strengthening metal-carbon and metal-oxygen interactions at the CNF-MOF interface. These improved interactions enabled a specific capacity of 295.4 mAh/g at 1 A/g. Furthermore, the NiCo MOF@NiCo CNF//ZIF CNF HSC device exhibits an energy density of 45.4 Wh/kg at a power density of 0.800 kW/kg and demonstrates good cycle stability, with a capacitance retention of 70% after 4000 cycles.

Acetylene black (AB) has also been utilized for the fabrication of hybrids with enhanced electrochemical performance [175]. The addition of AB into the NiCo-MOF was found to be conducive for increasing the specific surface area from 37.13 m²/g to 63.29 m²/g with mesoporous structure. The NiCo-MOF/AB composites exhibit a high specific capacitance of 916.1 F/g at 1 A/g, excellent rate capability, and cycling stability compared to pure NiCo-MOF (664.6 F/g at 1 A/g). Additionally, an ASC device constructed using these composites achieved a maximum energy density of 33.84 Wh/kg at a power density of 750 W/kg and demonstrated good cycling stability with 85.25% of the initial capacitance retained after 5000 cycles.

In addition to carbonaceous materials, other functional materials such as MXenes and layered double hydroxides (LDHs) have also been integrated with BMOFs to enhance SC performance [40,115,116]. Han and his group [40] reported NiCo-MOF/MXene heterostructures by assembling 2D ultrathin NiCo-MOF nanosheets onto exfoliated MXene sheets through room temperature ultrasonication. Morphological analyses showed that the simple room temperature ultrasonication process minimized the aggregation of 2D layered NiCo BMOF structure and stacking problem of MXene sheets in the NiCo-MOF/ M_{10} heterostructure (Fig. 8a–d). The resulting 2D heterostructure exhibited improved capacitance of 1176.8 F/g at 1 A/g compared with the pristine MOF (653.4 F/g at 1 A/g). It is worth noting that the optimum amount of MXene dosage (10 mg) and Ni/Co ion ratio in the 2D heterostructure (NiCo-MOF/ M_{10}) played a critical role in obtaining the maximum capacitive performance (Fig. 8e and f). The ASC device fabricated by using NiCo-MOF/ M_{10} as a positive electrode and AC as a negative electrode delivered the maximum energy density of 34.4 Wh/kg with the capacitance retention of 87.1% after 10,000 GCD cycles.

Recently, hybrid architectures combining metal hydroxides or LDHs with MOFs have attracted increasing attention for SC applications [176–178]. Although these studies are based on monometallic MOFs, they provide useful design principles for BMOF-based electrodes. For instance, Zou et al., [178] reported the room temperature synthesis of NiCo hydroxide@ Ni-MOF hollow prisms. The resulting hollow architecture, composed of vertically aligned Ni-MOF nanosheets, suppressed nanosheet aggregation and increased the exposure of electroactive sites. Benefiting from this hierarchical structure, the NiCo hydroxide@ Ni-MOF electrode delivered a specific capacitance of 1610 F/g at 1 A/g. The assembled ASC device delivered an energy density of 49.4 Wh/kg at a power density of 825 W/kg and retained 84% of its initial capacitance after 5000 cycles. Extending this concept to bimetallic systems, Xie and

Fig. 7. (a and b) SEM, (c) TEM images of Mn-Ni(3-HPCA) MOF/HA-CNT hybrid, (d) CV curves of Mn-Ni(3-HPCA) MOF/HA-CNT//XGnP solid-state ASC device in different potential window ranging from 0.7 to 1.7 V, (e) CV curves of the device at different scan rates with the potential window of 1.7 V, (f) GCD profiles at 0.3 A/g under different potential windows, (g and h) GCD profiles and specific capacitance variation at different current densities, (i) Cycling stability test of the ASC device (XRD patterns of the electrode material before and after 10,000 cycles – inset), (j) schematic illustration showing the synthesis of Mn-Ni(3-HPCA) MOF/HA-CNT hybrid, assembly of solid-state ASC device and the illumination of the LED device powered by ASC device. (Reproduced with permission [173] Copyright 2024, American Chemical Society).

Fig. 8. SEM images of (a) pristine multilayered $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene, (b) pristine NiCo-MOF, (c) SEM, and (d) TEM images of NiCo-MOF/M₁₀, (e) specific capacitance variation as a function of current density with different MXene dosage, (f) specific capacitance variation as a function of current density for NiCo-MOF/MXene hybrid with different Ni/Co ratio(s) (Reproduced with permission [40] Copyright 2023, Royal Society of Chemistry). SEM images of (g) Ni_3Co_2 -LDH, (h) Ni_3Co_2 -MOF, (i) Ni-LDH, (j) Ni_3Co_2 -MOF@Ni-LDH, and (k) relative contributions of surface and diffusion-controlled charge storage processes determined from CV curves recorded at different scan rates, (l) Ragone plot, and (m) cycling stability of NiCo-MOF@Ni-LDH//AC ASC device (Reproduced with permission [116] Copyright 2024, American Chemical Society).

his coworkers [116] reported the flower-like NiCo-BMOF hybrid with Ni LDH (NiCo-MOF@Ni-LDH). Interestingly, the NiCo BMOF was first synthesized from NiCo-LDH by using the reverse design approach followed by the hydrothermal synthesis to obtain NiCo-MOF@Ni-LDH. The Ni/Co molar ratio strongly influenced BMOF morphology. When the molar ratio of Ni^{2+} is higher, the resulting BMOF exhibits a relatively smoother surface morphology, whereas higher Co^{2+} content leads to the formation of more irregular surface structure. At the optimized Ni:Co ratio of 3:2, Ni_3Co_2 -MOF formed 2D nanosheets with a thickness of ~ 7 – $10\ \text{nm}$ (Fig. 8h). The Ni_3Co_2 -MOF@Ni-LDH heterostructure showed the flower-like morphology with the particle size of approx. $5\ \mu\text{m}$

(Fig. 8j). Notably, the metal-ion composition affected nanosheet thickness, which is expected to influence electrolyte-ion diffusion. Owing to the synergistic interactions, Ni_3Co_2 -MOF@Ni-LDH hybrid material exhibited the higher surface area ($27.04\ \text{m}^2/\text{g}$) compared with the pristine Ni_3Co_2 -MOF ($15.72\ \text{m}^2/\text{g}$). As a result, the Ni_3Co_2 -MOF@Ni-LDH electrode material exhibited the specific capacitance of $1880\ \text{F/g}$ at $1\ \text{A/g}$ which is 42.9% higher than the pristine Ni_3Co_2 -MOF ($1316\ \text{F/g}$ at $1\ \text{A/g}$). The CV curves were recorded at scan rates of 5 – $100\ \text{mV/s}$, showed anodic and cathodic peak shifts toward more positive and negative potentials, respectively, indicating polarization effects and kinetic limitations at higher scan rates. Fig. 8k demonstrates the relative

contribution of surface and diffusion-controlled processes from CV curves recorded at different scan rates. The ASC device (NiCo-MOF@Ni-LDH//AC) achieved the maximum energy density of 69.9 Wh/kg at a power density of 0.799 kW/kg, while maintaining 75.6% capacitance retention after 5000 consecutive charge-discharge cycles at 7 A/g (Fig. 8l and m).

3.2. BMOFs-derived metal oxide/hydroxides and their composites

BMOFs are commonly used to derive metal oxides/hydroxides for SC applications. The derived materials can be obtained in different structural morphologies through controlled calcination processes including multilayer core-shell microspheres [179], ultrathin nanosheets [180], and nanoflowers [181,182]. The resultant derived materials often expose more active sites, which provide shorter pathways for electron transfer and diffusion, leading to improved SC performance. Liu et al., [183] used M_2 (2,5-dihydroxy-1,4-benzenedicarboxylic) linker to construct highly porous bimetallic Ni–Co MOF-74 derived γ -Ni-Co double hydroxide by employing facile hydrothermal approach. The optimum mole ratio between the initial Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} played a key role in achieving excellent energy storage performance. The 65% Ni-35% Co MOF-74 (65Ni-MOF-74) delivered the highest capacity of 875 C/g at 1 A/g using 2 M KOH aqueous electrolyte in a three-electrode open cell along with the excellent cycling stability retaining 90.1% capacitance after 5000 cycles at 20 A/g. Further, the ASC device was assembled using 65Ni-MOF-74 as a positive electrode and N-doped carbon as negative electrode which demonstrated the high energy density of 81 Wh/kg at 1.9 kW/kg and impressively retaining 42 Wh/kg at a high-power density of 11.5 kW/kg.

Han et al. [184] rationally designed the growth of bimetallic $Co_{1-x}Fe_x$ -MOF-74 on Ni foam via an in situ interfacial method by varying the ratios of Co/Fe. This MOF was subsequently converted into bamboo-shoot-like α -Co(OH) $_2$ /CoFe $_2$ O $_4$ through an alkaline etching process, while preserving structural integration. Among the different varied ratios, CF-0.75/NF displayed the high areal capacitance of 3941 mF/cm 2 at 2 mA/cm 2 with good rate capability and cycling stability in a three-electrode system using 1 M KOH. The assembled ASC device (CF-0.75//AC) delivered the high areal energy density of 0.16 mWh/cm 2 at a power density of 0.756 mW/cm 2 . In another report, a NiCoLDH@Ni(OH) $_2$ heterostructure was derived from NiCo-MOF through an alkalinization treatment [185]. By leveraging the synergistic effects of both the components, the ASC device based on NiCo-LDH@Ni(OH) $_2$ //AC delivered the energy density of 30.6 Wh/kg at a power density of 0.799 kW/kg with the capacitance retention of 89% after 5000 repetitive charge-

discharge cycles. In an interesting approach by Dai et al., [186] Ni-Co-Mn ternary LDH was prepared by using CoMn bimetallic MOF followed by Ni^{2+} hydrolytic etching. This produced a hollow structure with surface-folded nanosheets, providing abundant redox-active sites and large SSA for efficient charge transport. Specifically, the role of Mn is highlighted in changing the interlayer spacing of LDH, which resulted in the facile diffusion of ions at the electrode/electrolyte interface, improved cycling stability and charge storage capabilities. The ASC device (NiCoMnLDH//AC) delivered the energy density of 64.3 Wh/kg at 0.799 kW/kg.

Mei and colleagues [187] employed an alkali hydrolysis strategy to convert a bimetallic Co/Ni-MOF into layered $Co_x/Ni_{1-x}(OH)_2$ with an optimized Co/Ni ratio (3:1) (Fig. 9a). The $Co/Ni(OH)_2$ -3:1 electrode exhibited capacitance of 1956 F/g at 5 A/g which is 15.4 and 1.6 times higher than MOF-derived pristine $Co(OH)_2$ and $Ni(OH)_2$, respectively. Although cycling stability was limited for the $Co/Ni(OH)_2$ -3:1 electrode (48% retention after 2000 cycles). Selective oxidation produced a $NiCo_2O_4/\beta-Ni_xCo_{1-x}(OH)_2/\alpha-Ni_xCo_{1-x}(OH)_2$ ternary composite, which exhibited excellent cycling stability when used in a solid-state Ni/Co-TC//AC device. Electrochemical measurements of the Ni/Co-TC//AC full cell device are shown in Fig. 9b-e. The device significantly improved the capacitance retention (90.7% of capacitance after 10,000 cycles) (Fig. 9d) and delivered a high energy density of 36.98 Wh/kg at 0.801 kW/kg (Fig. 9e).

Besides NiCo-MOF-derived hydroxides and oxides, BMOFs incorporating other transition metals such as Mn, Fe, and V have also been developed [188,189]. Bhosale and co-workers [188] recently used a facile hydrothermal method to synthesize $MnFe_2$ MOF using terephthalic acid as the linker in DMF media and further annealed the material at 500 °C to obtain MOF-derived $MnFe_2O_4$. However, the $MnFe_2$ -MOF electrode exhibited superior electrochemical properties (1226 F/g at 1 mA/cm 2) compared with derived $MnFe_2O_4$ (865 F/g at 1 mA/cm 2) due to the presence of more active sites and extremely porous structure in the $MnFe_2$ -MOF. The ASC device constructed with $MnFe_2$ -MOF as an anode and AC as a cathode ($MnFe_2$ -MOF//AC) displayed a specific capacitance of 91.87 F/g at a current density of 1 A/g, along with a specific energy of 32.67 Wh/kg at a power density of 1 kW/kg. For example, Jeong et al., [189] synthesized Co-V-MOF with a microflower morphology using dual-linker (Trimesic-4,5-imidazole dicarboxylic acid (H3IMDC)) via sono-hydrothermal method. The Co-V-MOF electrode material showed exceptionally high specific capacitance of 1711.1 F/g at 1 A/g benefiting from unique dual-layered 3D-on-2D structure. The electrochemical kinetic analysis showed that the charge storage in Co-V-MOF was dominated by a diffusion-controlled process (88.52%), with a smaller

Fig. 9. (a) A schematic illustration for the formation of $NiCo_2O_4/\beta-Ni_xCo_{1-x}(OH)_2/\alpha-Ni_xCo_{1-x}(OH)_2$ ternary composites, (b) CV, (c) GCD curves of the full cell device, (d) Specific capacitance variation as a function of current density, and (e) Ragone plot of the ASC device (Reproduced with permission [187]), Copyright 2018, American Chemical Society.

contribution from capacitive behavior (11.48%). The ASC device Co-V-MOF//AC operated up to 1.2 V, delivering a specific capacitance of 187.5 F/g and an energy density of 70.65 Wh/kg at a power density of 0.835 kW/kg, respectively.

The BMOF-derived materials that are uniformly embedded within and inherently coated by a conductive carbon matrix are of great importance. For example, Jin-Da et al., [130] synthesized a flower-like porous NiCo-BTC MOF on Ni foam via cathodic electrodeposition, which after KOH etching yielded a carbon-coated mixed NiCo-hydroxide (C@NiCo-hydroxide/NF). The C@NiCo-hydroxide/NF electrode

delivered 1825 F/g at 1 A/g and maintained 1216 F/g even at a high current density of 15 A/g, with 75.6% capacitance retention after 8000 consecutive cycles. The calcination temperature is another critical factor in deriving composite electrode materials from BMOFs used as sacrificial agents [190]. NiO/NiCo₂O₄ nanocomposite obtained at calcination temperature of 300 °C delivered the specific capacitance of 2461 F/g while the same composite calcined at 400 °C exhibited 2180 F/g at 1 A/g current density.

BMOF-derived oxides/hydroxides are often integrated with MXenes, conductive carbonaceous materials, or LDHs to improve interfacial

Fig. 10. (a) Schematic illustration for the formation of Ni-Fe-O/NPC@PCNF (positive electrode) and Fe₂O₃/NPC@PCNF (negative electrode), (b) XRD pattern of Ni-Fe-O/NPC@PCNFs-400, (c) TEM image of Ni-Fe-MOFs@PCNFs-400, (d) Ragone plot of the ASC device, and (e) digital image of a red LED illuminated by two devices connected in series. (Reproduced with permission [192], Copyright 2023, Elsevier). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

coupling, reduce resistance, and enhance electrode utilization in SCs. For instance, Yang and co-workers [191] reported NiCo-ZIF-67 BMOF on MXene and subsequently converted it into a NiCo double hydroxide/MXene composite (MXene/NiCoZDH). The as-obtained MXene/NiCo-ZDH composite delivered a higher specific capacitance of 877 F/g than the individual counterparts, such as MXene/NiCo-ZIF-67 (460 F/g), NiCoZDH (354 F/g), NiCo-ZIF-67 (130 F/g), and MXene (15 F/g) at 1 A/g. Further, the ASC device was assembled which delivered the energy density of 34 Wh/kg at 748 W/kg with a capacitance retention of 93.3% after 30,000 cycles. The excellent electrochemical performance was attributed to strong interfacial coupling between NiCo hydroxide and MXene layers via the formation of chemical bonds. The anchoring of NiCo-ZDH on the negatively charged surface of MXene surface improved interfacial contact, exposed more active sites, improved ionic diffusion and charge transport.

Meanwhile, Kim et al., [192] utilized porous carbon nanofibers (PCNFs) as the template material for the vertical growth of bimetallic Ni-Fe MOF (Ni-Fe MOFs@PCNFs) which was annealed at 400 °C to obtain 3D nanostructure of Ni-Fe-O/nanoporous carbon (NPC)@PCNFs (Ni-Fe-O/NPC@PCNFs-400) (Fig. 10a). The XRD pattern of Ni-Fe-O/NPC@PCNFs-400 and the TEM image of Ni-Fe MOFs@PCNFs are shown in Fig. 10b and c. The porous, vertically integrated Ni-Fe-O/NPC@PCNFs-400 enabled rapid ion transport and functioned as a free-standing electrode without binders or current collectors. It delivered the specific capacitance of 1419 F/g at 1 A/g with 88.5% retention after 10,000 cycles in 3 M KOH. Further, the ASC device was assembled by utilizing Ni-Fe-O/NPC@PCNFs-400 as the positive electrode and Fe₂O₃/NPC@PCNFs as the negative electrode delivered a high energy density of 41.3 Wh/kg at 892.2 W/kg, capable of powering a red LED when two devices were connected in series (Fig. 10d and e).

In addition to the carbonaceous-based materials and MXenes, LDHs have also emerged as effective supports for the growth of BMOFs and their derived oxides/hydroxide. Li and co-workers [193] synthesized NiCoC/O-NiCoAl LDH composite using NiCo-MOF as a precursor. The NiCo-MOF was pyrolyzed at high temperature under N₂ atmosphere to yield bimetallic oxides/carbides. Subsequently, NiCoAl LDH nanosheets were grown on the surface of NiCoC/O, producing a 3D nanoflower-like structure of NiCoC/O-NiCoAl LDH. The incorporation of LDH sheets prevented the aggregation of 3D nanoflower-like NiCoC/O-NiCoAl LDH composite and resulted in the increased SSA compared with the individual counterparts. In a three-electrode system, the composite material exhibited the specific capacitance of 2400 F/g at 1 A/g. The ASC device constructed by using NiCoC/O-NiCoAl LDH composite as a positive electrode and AC as a negative electrode delivered the energy density of 80 Wh/kg at a power density of 750 W/kg.

3.3. BMOFs-derived chalcogenides (S, Se, and Te) and their composites

BMOFs have also emerged as versatile precursors for deriving bimetallic chalcogenides such as sulfides (S), selenides (Se), and tellurides (Te). They are usually derived by employing thermal treatment under inert atmosphere or chemical transformation under the presence of chalcogen precursor, enabling the replacement of organic linkers and partial/complete conversion of metal nodes into corresponding metal chalcogenides. After transformation, BMOFs-derived chalcogenides retain the porous morphology and high surface area of their parent frameworks, providing abundant electroactive sites, efficient ion diffusion pathways, and richer redox activity, which collectively contribute to enhanced charge storage and superior cycling stability in SCs.

Wang and co-workers [194] synthesized ZIF-67 with a rhombic dodecahedron structure, which was then etched by Ni²⁺ and subsequently sulfurized to yield amorphous CoNi₂S₄ nanocages. These CoNi₂S₄ nanocages retained the original rhombic dodecahedral morphology of the ZIF-67, along with the vertically aligned nanosheets on the shell. The as-obtained CoNi₂S₄ electrode material exhibited high specific capacitance of 1890 F/g at 4 A/g. When assembled into a full ASC device, the

cell delivered an energy density of 35 Wh/kg at a power density of 0.640 kW/kg. The excellent electrochemical performance has been ascribed to the synergistic effect of bimetals, unique morphology and amorphous nature of the electrode material. Further, nitrogen doping improved the capacitive performance of BMOFs derived NiCo₂S₄ [195]. Hollow N-doped NiCo₂S₄ spheres (HN₂CMS) were synthesized by growing ZIF-67 (~300 nm polyhedral) on NF, followed by a two-step hydrothermal process. The binder-free HN₂CMS electrode delivered 938.1 C/g at 1 A/g in 3 M KOH. An ASC device (HN₂CMS//AC) achieved 51.2 Wh/kg at 0.800 kW/kg and retained 81.1% capacitance after 5000 cycles.

NiCo BMOF-derived sulfides have been extensively studied. Recent research has expanded to other bimetallic systems as well such as Cu-Co [196], and Zn-Co [197] based BMOF-derived sulfides. Lee et al., [196] synthesized hierarchical CuCo₂S₄ ultrathin nanosheet arrays on NF by first growing MOF derived CuCo₂ LDHs, which were then converted into CuCo₂S₄ via anion exchange process using Na₂S as a sulfur precursor. The CuCo₂S₄ ultrathin nanosheet electrode material displayed the specific capacity of ~409.2 mAh/g at 3 mA/cm² and excellent rate capability of ~77.9% at a high current density of 50 mA/cm² in 2 M KOH electrolyte. The CV curves of CuCo₂S₄ nanosheet electrode exhibited a typical oxidation (~0.47 V) and reduction (~0.14 V) peaks vs. Ag/AgCl, indicating the battery type behavior of CuCo₂S₄ nanosheet arrays. For assembling the ASC device, CuCo₂S₄ was used as a positive electrode and iron oxide anchored N-doped graphene (Fe₂O₃/NG) was used as a negative electrode and the potential window was broadened up to 1.6 V. The solid-state ASC device delivered an exceptionally high energy density of ~89.6 Wh/kg at ~663 W/kg and superior cycling stability with a capacitance retention of ~91.5% after 10,000 cycles.

The precise control of metal composition, chemical etching and sulfurization process leads to the desired morphology of the BMOF and their derived material. Zhang and coworkers [198] synthesized double-shelled zinc-cobalt sulphide (Zn-Co-S) rhombic dodecahedral cages (RDCs) by preparing yolk-shelled zinc/cobalt-based zeolitic imidazolate framework (Zn/Co-ZIF) RDCs, followed by controlled chemical etching, and hydrothermal sulfurization. The Zn/Co molar ratio in the obtained composite was controlled and the synergistic impact of the compositional and double-shelled structure resulted into enhanced SC performance, demonstrating high specific capacitance (1266 F/g at 1 A/g), good rate capability, and long-term cycling stability (91% retention over 10,000 cycles).

Interestingly, ZIF-67, a cobalt-based zeolitic imidazolate framework, has been widely used both as a template for BMOFs and as a precursor for deriving ternary metal sulfides [199,200]. Incorporating additional transition metal ions via ion-exchange or secondary growth strategies, resulting into additional redox-active sites, improved conductivity and superior cycling stability. For instance, hollow rod-like NiCoMn ternary metal sulfide nanosheets were derived from ZIF-67 MOF by employing etching/ion exchange reaction followed by the sulfurization process [200]. The optimized NiCoMn-S electrode material in 1 M KOH exhibited specific capacitance of 2098.2 F/g much higher than the corresponding NiCoMn hydroxides (1162 F/g) at 1 A/g, as well as the monometallic Co-S and bimetallic NiCo-S and CoMn-S counterparts. This superior performance was attributed to the stronger synergistic interaction among Ni, Co, and Mn centers and optimized metal ratio and the preserved hollow-rod like nanosheet morphology. The assembled ASC device (NiCoMn-S//AC) achieved energy density of 50.0 Wh/kg at 0.850 kW/kg which is higher than the energy density achieved by Cu (NiCo₂)₂S₄/Ni₃S₄ 3D hierarchical hollow heterostructure (positive electrode) with AC (negative electrode) (Cu(NiCo₂)₂S₄/Ni₃S₄//AC) 40.8 Wh/kg at a power density of 0.785 kW/kg [201].

Integrating BMOF-derived chalcogenides with other functional materials has emerged as an effective strategy to enhance the overall electrochemical performance of SC electrodes. Yan et al., [132] used bimetallic Co/Ni MOF precursors to prepare double-layered yolk-shell microspheres (NiCo₂S₄-Ni₉S₈-C DYMs) on amorphous carbon. The Co/

Ni-MOF yolk-shell microspheres were first obtained hydrothermally by using self-template bimetallic $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}(\text{HBTC})(\text{DMF})_2$, which was then converted into $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4\text{-NiO-C}$ via two-step calcination, and finally transformed into $\text{NiCo}_2\text{S}_4\text{-Ni}_9\text{S}_8\text{-C}$ through sulfuration (Fig. 11a). The SEM images revealed that the $\text{NiCo}_2\text{S}_4\text{-Ni}_9\text{S}_8\text{-C}$ DYMs retained the structural features of their $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4\text{-NiO-C}$ DYMs precursors, exhibiting a distinctive double-layered yolk-shell architecture (Fig. 11b and c). Likewise, HRTEM images also confirmed the hierarchical structure of the $\text{NiCo}_2\text{S}_4\text{-Ni}_9\text{S}_8\text{-C}$ DYMs, showing microspheres composed of interconnected nanoparticles with lattice spacings of 0.235 and 0.285 nm, corresponding to the (4 0 0) planes of NiCo_2S_4 and the (222) planes of Ni_9S_8 , respectively (Fig. 11d-f). The SAED pattern indicated the coexistence and polycrystalline nature of NiCo_2S_4 and Ni_9S_8 in the DYMs (Fig. 11g). The hybrid SC (HSC) was assembled using $\text{NiCo}_2\text{S}_4\text{-Ni}_9\text{S}_8\text{-C}$ DYMs (positive) and rGO hydrogel (negative) extended up to 1.6 V (Fig. 11h). The CV curves of the HSC showed contributions from both faradaic and EDLC behavior (Fig. 11i). GCD profiles at different current densities showed good electrochemical reversibility with the specific capacitance calculated to be 143.5 F/g at 2 A/g (Fig. 11j). The device demonstrated an energy density of 51.0 Wh/kg at a high-power density of 1.4 kW/kg, with the capacitance retention of 84.5% after 5000 cycles at a current density of 6 A/g (Fig. 11k and l).

Mai and co-workers [202] synthesized Zn/Co BMOF nanosheets on CC using 2-methylimidazole organic linker, which after annealing and sulfuration with thioacetamide yielded hierarchical $\text{Zn}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{S}$ nanoparticles embedded ultrathin N-doped carbon ($\text{Zn}_{0.76}\text{Co}_{0.24}\text{S-NC}$). The binder-free electrode material exhibited the high specific capacitance of 2133.2 F/g at 1.25 A/g. The assembled ASC device ($\text{Zn}_{0.76}\text{Co}_{0.24}\text{S-NC}/\text{mesoporous carbon (MPC)}$) achieved very high energy density of 92.59 Wh/kg at 846.2 W/kg. Similarly, the ASC device assembled with Co/Zn-MOF derived Co/Zn-S polyhedron embedded in rGO sheets and AC (Co/Zn-S@rGO//AC) achieved an ultra-high energy density of 91.8 Wh/kg at a power density of 0.800 kW/kg and retained 80.3% capacity after 8000 cycles [203].

Among various carbonaceous materials, carbon nanotubes (CNTs)

have been widely combined with BMOF-derived sulfides to construct conductive hybrid electrodes for SC application [113,204]. Yang and co-workers [204] reported 3D interconnected MWCNT/Ni-Mn-S hybrid derived from MWCNT/Ni/Mn-MOF-74 by a facile hydrothermal approach. The MWCNT/Ni/Mn-MOF-74 precursor is highly stable due to the covalent interactions between Ni and C which was further converted to MWCNT/Ni-Mn-S through vulcanization treatment. The MWCNT/Ni-Mn-S hybrid, prepared with the optimal Ni: Mn (3:2) ratio, exhibited a high specific capacity of 1041 mAh/g at 1 A/g. The ASC device (MWCNT/Ni-Mn-S//AC) showed the high energy density of 25.33 Wh/kg at 829 W/kg with a capacitance retention of 93.3% after 20,000 cycles. Recently, Lao et al., [205] developed a novel Ni $(\text{Co})_3\text{S}_4$ @MXene hybrid by loading BMOF-derived sulfides onto 1D MXene fibers prepared via KOH treatment. The strong interfacial coupling between MXene and BMOF-derived Ni $(\text{Co})_3\text{S}_4$ through Ti-O-Co bonds, which enhanced conductivity, redox activity, and charge transfer. The Ni $(\text{Co})_3\text{S}_4$ @MXene hybrid electrode material showed the capacity value of 829.4 C/g at 1 A/g in KOH electrolyte. Further, the assembled ASC device (Ni $(\text{Co})_3\text{S}_4$ @MXene-fibers//AC) delivered the energy density of 63.3 Wh/kg at 850 W/kg.

Recently, an in situ strategy was developed to synthesize CoMnSe on NF as a binder-free electrode [206]. Co-MOF was first grown on NF and converted into CoMn-MOF via Mn ion exchange, then selenized to form CoMnSe. Co-MOF@NF initially forms densely packed rods with 2-methyl imidazole (2MeIM), while Mn substitution transforms the structure into a dendrite-like morphology in CoMn-MOF@NF. The CoMnSe@NF-2 h electrode exhibits high gravimetric (519 C/g at 1 A/g) and areal capacity (1714 mC/cm² at 1 mA/cm²) with a capacitance retention of 87% after 5000 cycles. It is noteworthy that the capacitive performance for BMOF-derived CoMnSe@NF-2 h (519 C/g at 1 A/g) is higher than the pristine CoMn-MOF@NF (128 C/g at 1 A/g). Further, the ASC device was fabricated using CoMnSe@NF-2 h as positive electrode and O,N,S@AC@NF as negative electrode (CoMnSe@NF-2 h//O,N,S@AC@NF), which delivered the maximum energy density of 35.47 Wh/kg and maximum power density of 11.5 kW/kg. The high

Fig. 11. (a) Schematic illustration for the synthesis of $\text{NiCo}_2\text{S}_4\text{-Ni}_9\text{S}_8\text{-C}$ DYMs, (b and c) SEM, (d-g) TEM images along with SAED pattern, (h) digital image of the assembled HSC device, (i) CV curves at different scan rates, (j) GCD profiles at different current densities (k and l) Ragone plot and cycling stability test for the HSC device. (Reproduced with permission [132], Copyright 2020, Elsevier).

performance was attributed to the large SSA leading to increased contact area, abundant redox-active sites, efficient electron transport facilitated by Se, and synergistic interactions among Co, Mn, and Se. In a related study [207], Ni-Fe-Mn-Se nanoboxes with a double-layer hollow architecture were fabricated using NiFe Prussian blue analogue (NiFe-PBA) as a structural template. A polydopamine (PDA) coating was introduced to stabilize the PBA core and provide anchoring sites for the in situ growth of NiMn-LDH, followed by etching with selenium acid to obtain Ni-Fe-Mn-Se nanocubes. This work demonstrates the advantage of extending BMOF-derived selenides to polymetallic composition, where multiple metal centers and Se collectively regulate the electronic structure and improve electrical conductivity. The Ni-Fe-Mn-Se nanocubes exhibited the high specific capacitance of 1433 F/g at 1 A/g. The assembled ASC delivered an energy density of 66.8 Wh/kg at a power density of 791 W/kg with 85% capacitance retention after 8000 cycles.

Mohammad et al., [208] synthesized $\text{Sn}_{0.17}\text{Co}_{0.83}\text{Se}_2$ nanorods (NRs) from BMOFs via anion exchange involving the insertion of Se_2^{2-} ions with an organic ligand in the MOF structure and subsequent annealing at

650 °C with selenium powder (Fig. 12a). TEM image revealed the agglomerated 1D and 2D NR morphology of $\text{Sn}_{0.17}\text{Co}_{0.83}\text{Se}_2$ with a thickness of ~40–50 nm (Fig. 12b). The symmetric flexible SC device was assembled with ([EMIM][BF₄] + PVDF) extending the potential window of 0–2.5 V ($\text{Sn}_{0.17}\text{Co}_{0.83}\text{Se}_2$ /[EMIM][BF₄]/ $\text{Sn}_{0.17}\text{Co}_{0.83}\text{Se}_2$) (Fig. 12c). The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) spectrum revealed that the ion diffusion capacitance contributes negligibly to the overall capacitance of the $\text{Sn}_{0.17}\text{Co}_{0.83}\text{Se}_2$ electrode (Fig. 12d). The CV curves of the device at different scan rates (Fig. 12e). From the GCD profiles, the specific capacitance is calculated to be 121.6 mF/cm² at a current density of 0.65 mA/cm² (Fig. 12f). The flexible symmetrical device delivered the energy density of 0.053 mWh/cm² at a power density 0.73 mW/cm² with the capacitance retention of 93.23% after 10,000 cycles (Fig. 12g and h).

Further, modification strategies such as defect engineering and transition metal doping have also been explored for enhancing the capacitive performance of BMOF-derived selenide [209,210]. The introduction of defects, such as vacancies, creates more electrochemical

Fig. 12. (a) Schematic illustration for the synthesis of $\text{Sn}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Se}_2$ NRs via anion exchange method, (b) TEM image of $\text{Sn}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Se}_2$ NRs, (c) digital image of the assembled symmetrical flexible cell ($\text{Sn}_{0.17}\text{Co}_{0.83}\text{Se}_2$ /[EMIM][BF₄]/ $\text{Sn}_{0.17}\text{Co}_{0.83}\text{Se}_2$). (d) EIS, (e) CV, (f) GCD profiles, (g) Ragone plot, and (h) cycling stability test for the symmetric cell. (Reproduced with permission [208], Copyright 2024, American Chemical Society).

active sites and facilitates the diffusion of electrolyte ions at the electrode/electrolyte interface. For example, trimetallic selenide ($V_a\text{-ZnSe}/\text{NiCoSe}_2$), derived from ZIF-8@ZIF-67 core-shell structure via Ni^{2+} etching followed by selenization and NaBH_4 reduction, was enriched with Se vacancies [209]. These vacancies improved conductivity, generated additional electrochemically active sites, and facilitated charge transfer. The optimized electrode material with 1 M concentration of NaBH_4 i.e., $V_1\text{-ZnSe}/\text{NiCoSe}_2$ exhibited the specific capacitance of 1563 F/g at 1 A/g in 6 M KOH electrolyte. The ASC device was assembled which delivered the specific capacitance of 201.2 F/g at 1 A/g with energy density of 41.9 Wh/kg at 750 W/kg. The device showed the capacitance retention of 85% after 8000 cycles at 5 A/g. DFT calculations further corroborated the role of Se vacancies in enhancing the electrochemical performance of the $V_1\text{-ZnSe}/\text{NiCoSe}_2$ electrode. The optimized defect model identified Se-vacancy sites within the $V_1\text{-ZnSe}/\text{NiCoSe}_2$ framework, while charge-density-difference analysis revealed pronounced interfacial charge redistribution after vacancy formation. The accumulation of electrons around the Se-vacancy sites suggests the generation of additional electrochemically active sites that enhance electron transfer and accelerate the reaction kinetics during the discharge process. Similar to defect engineering, transition metal doping can also improve conductivity, and introduce additional electroactive sites, thereby further boosting charge storage performance. Han and co-workers [210] reported Mo-doped Ni—Co selenide nanosheets derived from ZIF-L oriented NiCo-LDH precursor followed by ion doping with selenization. The resulting Mo-(Ni,Co)Se nanosheet array achieved the specific capacity of 1.68 mAh/cm² at 2 mA/cm². An ASC device delivered the energy density of 2.59 mWh/cm² at 1.704 mW/cm² with the excellent capacitance retention of 97% after 10,000 cycles.

Beyond the above discussed modification strategies, BMOF-derived selenides have also been integrated with conductive supports for improving the SC performance. Li et al., [149] synthesized CuCoSe nanosheet arrays on rGO modified NF via a self-sacrificial CuCo-MOF template followed by controlled selenization (CuCoSe@rGO-NF). The CuCoSe@rGO-NF hybrid electrode exhibited high capacitance of 1521.6 F/g at 1 A/g with 99.5% retention after 6000 cycles. Similarly, Ni-Zn-Co-Se hollow and porous nanosheets grown on rGO-modified NF achieved enhanced electrochemical performance, where the assembled hybrid SC delivered 74.6 Wh/kg at a power density of 0.796 kW/kg, highlighting the effectiveness of integrating BMOF-derived selenides with conductive carbon supports [211].

Beyond rGO as a carbonaceous support, nitrogen doped carbon (NC) layers have been integrated with CuCoSe derived from BMOFs [212]. Benefitting from the synergistic effects, the (CuCo)Se/NC hybrid achieved specific capacity of 121.4 C/g at 1 A/g. Extending this approach, Du et al., [213] designed a 3D/2D Ni-Co-Se/MXene heterostructure by integrating MOF-derived 3D Ni-Co-Se microspheres with 2D MXene nanosheets via solvothermal growth and hydrothermal selenization. The hybrid leveraged MXene's conductivity and Ni-Co-Se's high capacity, delivering 1832.4 C/g at 1 A/g with the excellent rate capability (85.3% at 20 A/g). The assembled ASC device (Ni-Co-Se/MXene-3//AC) achieved a fairly high energy density of 76.8 Wh/kg at a power density of 0.860 kW/kg, outperforming most of the state-of-the-art advanced electrode materials. This superior performance is attributed to the hierarchical architecture, which prevents MXene restacking, enhances conductivity, and provides abundant active sites.

Alongside carbon-based materials and MXene, integrating BMOF-derived selenides with metal oxides has also proven effective in enhancing electrochemical performance. For instance, (NiCo)Se₂ nanospheres decorated with rare earth oxide (CeO₂) were synthesized using mixed-ligands (i.e., biphenyl-4,4'-dicarboxylic acid (BPDC) and terephthalic acid (PTA)) via solvothermal followed by hydrothermal selenization [214]. BPDC was introduced as a nucleation-modulating ligand to partially replace PTA, suppressing lateral MOF growth through steric hindrance. The PTA:BPDC (3:7) ratio was optimized to prepare NiCo-MOF-x-CeO₂, which was then hydrothermally selenized to yield (NiCo)

Se₂-3:7-CeO₂ hybrid. Exploiting strong interfacial synergy, the optimized electrode delivered 2715 F/g at 1 A/g in 6 M KOH electrolyte, and the assembled HSC achieved an energy density of 45.9 Wh/kg at a power density of 0.747 kW/kg.

BMOF-derived tellurides have recently emerged as promising electrode materials for high-performance SCs. Poudel et al., [215] synthesized BMOF-derived ZnCoTe integrated into nitrogen doped carbon (ZnCoTe-N-C), which has been used as cathode and ZnCo nanoparticles encapsulated in N-doped CNTs (ZnCo-NPs-N-CNTs) as anode for constructing HSC device. Incorporation of MoS₂ nanosheets into the cathode enhanced active sites, improving both capacitance and stability of the electrode. The HSC device achieved a high specific energy density of 108.41 Wh/kg at power density of 1.08 kW/kg, maintaining 93.6% of its initial capacitance after 20,000 cycles. Similarly, Fotouhi et al., [216] synthesized Ni-Zn-Te nanorod arrays on rGO modified NF, from Ni-Zn-MOF precursors. The in situ reduction of GO to rGO formed a 3D conductive network that supported uniform Ni-Zn-MOF growth and enhanced electron transport during redox processes, and tellurization further enhanced conductivity. The resulting Ni-Zn-Te/rGO/NF electrode achieved 265 mAh/g at 2 A/g, and the ASC device exhibited 77.9 Wh/kg at 1.44 kW/kg with 90% capacitance retention after 7000 cycles. These studies highlight that hybridization with carbonaceous materials or incorporation of additional active components, such as MoS₂ or rGO, can significantly enhance the electrochemical performance of BMOF-derived tellurides, although their exploration in SCs remains limited.

3.4. BMOFs-derived phosphides and their composites

Similar to BMOF-derived oxides/hydroxides, sulfides, selenides, and tellurides, BMOF-derived transition metal phosphides (TMPs) have also shown great promise as SC electrodes. Specifically, NiCoP-based materials have shown excellent potential as positive electrodes in ASCs, with performance strongly influenced by electrode design, morphology and electrolyte choice [217–220]. Kavian et al., [217] demonstrated that NiCo-MOF derived NiCoP outperformed mono-metallic NiP, delivering a higher capacitance (1456 vs. 1286 F/g at 2 A/g) due to additional Co redox activity and synergistic effects between Ni and Co. The NiCoP//AC ASC device showed energy density of 36.87 Wh/kg and a power density of 2.25 kW/kg. NiCoP microflowers with mesoporous structures (6–10 μm) delivered a fairly high capacitance of 1153 F/g at 1 A/g and an energy density of 48.4 Wh/kg at a power density of 0.275 kW/kg [218]. Similarly, solvent-regulated synthesis showed that NiCo-MOF microflowers (1086 F/g) outperformed microspheres (613 F/g) and nanosheets (548 F/g) at 1 A/g, and their conversion to NiCoP further boosted capacitance to 1592 F/g at 1 A/g, with the NiCoP//AC device reaching 51.2 Wh/kg at 0.749 kW/kg [219]. While activated carbon is most commonly employed as negative electrode due to its high surface area and EDLC behavior, biomass-derived porous carbon has also shown potential as a promising anode. Yang et al., [221] assembled NiCoP//coconut shell derived carbon based ASC device with an extended voltage window of 1.7 V, delivering 55.01 Wh/kg at 0.849 kW/kg with 86.12% capacitance retention after 10,000 cycles in 6 M KOH.

In addition to synergistic Ni—Co interactions and morphology engineering, innovative strategies such as the use of ionic liquids (both as structure directing agents for NiCo-MOF synthesis and electrolytes) have further boosted electrochemical performance. For example, NiCo-MOF was synthesized with the assistance of butyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (BMIM-TFSI) ionic liquid and 2,6-naphthalene dicarboxylic acid as an organic linker, and subsequently converted into NiCoP through solvothermal and phosphidation methods (Fig. 13a). In this strategy, BMIM-TFSI was employed as a dual-function agent – serving as a structure directing agent to induce porous NiCoP architectures via the Kirkendall effect, and as part of the electrolyte (KOH/ BMIM TFSI) to improve charge transfer kinetics [220]. The CV curves of NiCo-P/ BMIM-TFSI@KOH and graphite were recorded in their respective potential windows (Fig. 13b). The resulting NiCoP electrode

Fig. 13. (a) Schematic illustration for the synthesis of NiCoP, (b) CV curves of NiCoP/ BMIM-TFSI@KOH and graphite in half-cell, (c) GCD profiles of ionic liquid HSC device at different current density, (d) Ragone plot of the device along with the comparison with previously reported literature. (Reproduced with permission [220], Copyright 2024, American Chemical Society).

delivered 821 F/g at 1 A/g in three-electrode system, while the corresponding device using graphite as the negative electrode delivered 104 F/g at 1 A/g, along with an energy density of 75.29 Wh/kg and excellent cycling stability of 97.9% retention after 12,000 cycles (Fig. 13c and d). These findings highlight that, alongside the synergistic chemistry and morphology of NiCoP electrodes, the careful selection of negative electrode and electrolyte system is equally critical for improving energy density and long-term cycling stability in BMOF-derived phosphide-based ASC devices.

As discussed, NiCo-based phosphides have been widely studied due to their compatible redox properties and strong Ni–Co synergistic interactions. Beyond NiCo systems, bimetallic MOFs such as NiMn-MOF [222] and MnCo-MOF [223] have also been explored for deriving phosphides. These transition metal combinations leverage the redox activity of Mn alongside the use of Ni or Co. Recently, Wang et al., [223] reported hierarchical nanoflower-like MnCo-P grown in situ on Ni foam via a two-step hydrothermal and chemical vapor deposition process, with hexamethylenetetramine (HMTA) as a surfactant. The optimum Mn:Co ratio (1:2) yielded a high specific capacitance of 2224.4 F/g at 1 A/g in 6 M KOH and an ASC device energy density of 87.83 Wh/kg at 0.757 kW/kg, surpassing the performance of many NiCoP based ASC devices [217–219]. However, research on leveraging Mn-based redox processes in BMOF-derived phosphides remains limited, highlighting an opportunity for further investigation to expand the range of high-performance electrode materials for SCs.

Like others, BMOF-derived phosphides have also been integrated with other functional supports such as carbon fibers, porous carbon, rGO, CNTs, MXenes, and other BMOFs to further improve SC performance [224–227]. Chhetri et al., [224] fabricated hollow carbon nanofibers (HCNFs) via core-shell electrospinning a polyacrylonitrile/

poly(methyl methacrylate) (PAN/PMMA) mixture. Ni–Fe based BMOFs were then grown on both inside and outside the HCNF channels. Subsequent phosphidation yielded Ni-Fe-P nanostructures uniformly decorating the inner and outer surfaces of the HCNFs. This unique dual-sided Ni-Fe-P/HCNF architecture not only shortened ion/electron transport pathways and enhanced interfacial reactions but also prevented carbon aggregation during the cycling test by avoiding π - π interaction, collectively leading to superior electrochemical performance as SC electrodes. The fabricated ASC device (Ni-Fe-P-C@HCNFs//Fe-P-C@HCNFs) delivered 176.6 F/g at 1 A/g with \sim 92.4% retention after 10,000 cycles, underscoring the effectiveness of BMOF-derived phosphide-carbon hybrids in achieving durable high-performance SCs.

Similarly, Xu et al., [228] synthesized hollow bimetallic phosphide ($\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{P}$) via etching and phosphorization of ZIF-67 at 350°C , achieving specific capacity of 548 C/g at 1 A/g in 2 M KOH. The corresponding ASC device ($\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{P}/\text{AC}$) delivered 31.52 Wh/kg at 0.700 kW/kg and excellent cycling stability (98.3% capacitance retention after 10,000 cycles). Further improvements were demonstrated in hollow NiCoP/rGO nanocomposite, which leveraged synergistic effects between NiCoP and rGO to achieve 250.9 mAh/g at 1 A/g with good rate capability (62.7% retention at 10 A/g). The ASC device reached 60.6 Wh/kg at 0.749 kW/kg and excellent cycling stability, retaining 83.7% of its capacitance after 10,000 cycles at 10 A/g [225]. In another strategy a zirconium-based MOF (UiO-66) was hybridized with GO/MXene to obtain GO/MXene@UiO-66 which was subsequently transformed into GO/MXene@NiZr-P through LDH formation and phosphorization [227]. The resulting hierarchical hybrid (GO/MXene@NiZrP) delivered a high capacitance of 2110 F/g at 1 A/g in 6 M KOH, which is higher than their individual GO/NiZr-LDH (1118.6 F/g) and MXene/NiZr-LDH (1194.2 F/g) counterparts. This improvement arises from

granular NiZrP which fills the gaps between the layered structure, preventing restacking and oxidation of GO and MXene sheets, exposes additional active edge sites and enhances ion accessibility. Moreover, GO and MXene serve as ion-reservoir platforms, promoting rapid ion and electron transport through the NiZrP active sites, thereby boosting overall charge transfer and electrochemical performance for SCs.

Beyond BMOF-derived phosphides, trimetallic phosphide embedded in conductive carbon matrices has also been studied [229]. FeNiCeP was embedded in a sulfur-containing carbon matrix on Ni foam (SC-FeNiCeP/NF) derived from high-valence metal engineered MOF materials via hydrothermal and chemical vapor deposition methods. The introduction of high valence Ce helped to regulate the charge transfer, while the S-containing carbon matrix provided a conductive and structurally stable framework. Benefitting from the trimetallic composition and nanoarray architecture, SC-FeNiCeP/NF electrode delivered an impressive capacitance of 2290 F/g at 1 A/g in 1 M KOH [229]. The assembled ASC device delivered an energy density of 30.22 Wh/kg at a power density of 805.86 W/kg. Similarly, CNTs grown on CC by CVD method provided a conductive and high surface area for MOF-derived $\text{ZnP}_2@CoP$ heterostructures, yielding 1600 F/g at 1 A/g [230]. Furthermore, the assembled ASC device demonstrated the energy density of 83.03 Wh/kg at a power density of 0.749 kW/kg. DFT further confirmed the superior charge storage capability of the bimetallic $\text{ZnP}_2@CoP$ (1012 F/cm²) compared to monometallic CoP (160 F/cm²), underscoring the strong synergistic effect of bimetallic systems with conductive carbon frameworks.

Beyond the commonly explored BMOF derivatives such as oxides, hydroxides, chalcogenides, phosphides and their composites, BMOFs have also been utilized as precursors for metal particles through controlled calcination. During this process, the organic ligand decomposes, and the metal centers are reduced to form well dispersed metal nanoparticles embedded in the carbonaceous matrix. Recently, Pan and co-workers [231] reported a new Mg/Zn BMOF ($\text{Mg}_x\text{Zn}_{5-x}\text{MOF}$) synthesized via solvothermal reaction using benzene-1,3,5-tricarboxylic acid. The optimized $\text{Mg}_2\text{Zn}_3\text{-MOF}$ was calcined, etched, and KOH activated to yield porous carbon (MZAPC-4) with a high surface area of 2127 m²/g and mesopores of 3–3.85 nm, enhancing conductivity and ion transport. The electrode material exhibited a capacitance of 468 F/g at 1 A/g and excellent rate performance (366 F/g at 100 A/g; 268 F/g at 300 A/g) in 6 M KOH. When assembled in a symmetric cell with 1 M $\text{Et}_4\text{NBF}_4/\text{AN}$ electrolyte, the device achieved a significantly higher energy density of 46.23 Wh/kg compared to 18.7 Wh/kg in aqueous 6 M KOH. Li and co-workers [232] further highlighted the benefits of integrating BMOFs with conductive carbon by developing Ni-Mn@C/rGO composite. The hybrid material was obtained by calcining a Ni-Mn BMOF at 1000 °C, where graphitized carbon encapsulated the Ni-Mn particles (~200 nm) while rGO sheets anchored and interconnected them into a conductive network. This architecture ensured uniform metal distribution, strong encapsulation of bimetals in the graphitized carbon layer, and enhanced charge transport. In an ASC using Ni-Mn@C/rGO as the positive electrode and a 3D rGO aerogel as the negative electrode, the device delivered a energy density of 24.1 Wh/kg at power densities of 0.089 kW/kg, along with excellent cycling stability (90% retention after 10,000 cycles). These studies show that bimetallic MOFs can be converted into porous carbon frameworks with improved conductivity and ion diffusion. Coupling BMOF-derived carbons with rGO further improves long-term stability, which is important for practical SC applications. The summary of the electrochemical performances of BMOFs, their composites and derived materials are given in Table 2. The effect of addition of second metal to the monometallic MOF structure is given in Table 3.

4. Factors affecting the performance of BMOFs-based SCs

4.1. Structural and composition factors

In BMOFs, the presence of two distinct metal centers profoundly modulates both the structural features and composition of the material in ways that directly impact electrochemical charge storage and kinetics [187,214,269,270]. At the atomic and molecular levels, mixed metals introduce synergistic redox activity because each metal species possesses unique valence chemistry and redox potentials. The coexistence of these redox centers expands the number of accessible faradaic processes, increasing pseudocapacitive contributions relative to monometallic frameworks. For instance, 1D NiCo BMOF nanobelts with an optimized Ni to Co metal ratio (NiCo-MOF-31) showed a remarkably higher specific capacitance of 1697.4 F/g at 1 A/g, outperforming their monometallic counterparts, Co-MOF (100.1 F/g) and Ni-MOF (1153.3 F/g). This study also underscores the critical role of metal composition optimization in achieving maximum electrochemical performance. Among the series of NiCo-MOF with varying metal ratios, 1D NiCo-MOF-31 demonstrated the highest capacitance compared to 1D NiCo-MOF-11 (1211.8 F/g), 1D NiCo-MOF-13 (1020.8 F/g), 1D NiCo-MOF-41 (916 F/g), and 1D NiCo-MOF-21 (626.7 F/g). These findings clearly confirm that the synergistic interaction between Ni and Co metal cations at an optimal ratio not only increases the density of redox-active sites but also enhances the electrical conductivity of the electrode material, thereby improving overall charge-storage performance [271]. Furthermore, compositional tuning alters the crystal morphology and pore architecture, promoting hierarchical micro/mesoporous structures that ease ion diffusion and increase accessible electroactive surface area. Apart from two metals, introduction of a third metal (e.g., Zn, Fe, Mn) into a Ni-Co backbone has been shown to substantially increase specific capacitances (e.g., >1100 F/g for Zn-Ni-Co MOFs) through modifications in morphology and defect populations that enable faster ion transport [272].

Meanwhile, the selection of organic linker plays a crucial role in modulating the coordination environment, electronic structure, and overall stability of BMOFs. The organic linkers containing carboxylates or imidazolates functional groups strengthen metal-ligand bonding and improve electrolyte ion accessibility, leading to improved structural stability and enhanced cycling stability. A recent study [273], systematically investigated the influence of different organic linkers namely 2-methylimidazole (HMIM; with N-donor atom embedded in the imidazole ring attached to a hydrophobic -CH₃ group), terephthalic acid (BDC; with O-donor atom), and 2-amino terephthalic acid (ABDC; with free O and N-donor atoms) on the formation and electrochemical performance of ZnCo-BMOF. The resulting structural, morphological, and electrochemical variations were attributed to differences in the electron-donating capabilities of the linkers. Among these, the imidazole-based ZnCo-BMOF (ZnCo-MOF-HMIM) demonstrated the superior specific capacity (176.8 mAh/g), surpassing those synthesized with BDC (66.7 mAh/g) and ABDC (102.6 mAh/g) at 1 A/g. The superior electrochemical performance of ZnCo-MOF-HMIM has been attributed to the strong coordination between N donor atom in the imidazole ligand which coordinates with the Zn²⁺ and Co²⁺ metal centers, which enhances electronic conductivity and ion accessibility. Furthermore, the ASC device (ZnCo-MOF-HMIM//AC) delivered an impressive energy density of 28.2 Wh/kg at a power density of 1025.4 W/kg, with 80% capacitance retention after 10,000 cycles at a current density of 10 A/g.

Recently, it has been demonstrated that the coordination modulator such as sodium acetate can significantly influence the pH of the reaction medium, thereby altering the structural, textural, surface charge, and electrochemical properties of the NiCo BMOFs [270]. The influence of pH on NiCo BMOF was systematically evaluated in a three-electrode configuration using 3 M KOH aqueous electrolyte. The specific capacitances of NiCo BMOFs electrodes at different pH levels of 3.5, 6.0, 7.0, and 8.5 were calculated to be 356.7, 576.4, 265.3, and 515.5 F/g,

Table 2
Summary of electrochemical performance of BMOFs, their composites and derived materials.

Electrode Composition	Electrolyte	E_{max} (Wh/ kg)	P at E_{max} (W/ kg)	Max C_{sp} (F/ g)	Current density (A/g)	C_{sp} @cycle	Ref
Carbon Based Composites							
Ni/Co-MOF-rGO nanocomposite	6 M KOH	72.8	42.5	860	1.0	91.6% @ 6000	[233]
NiCo ₂ S ₄ /V-MOF@rGO	3 M KOH	61.1	800	1844	1.0	98% @ 3000	[234]
CuFeBTC/S-GNS composites	1 M Na ₂ SO ₄	96.57	1595.12	1164.3	1.8	92.5% @ 10,000	[167]
Cu@Fe-MOF/NF	PVA-KOH gel	44.20	2.743	562.01	3	89.5% @ 5000	[235]
Co/Zn-S@rGO composite	1 M KOH	91.8	800	1640	1.0	90.3% @ 8000	[203]
M-MOFs//CNTs-COOH Composites	3 M KOH	61.8	725	1450	1.0	86% @ 5000	[172]
YV-MOF@CNT Composite	2 M KOH	60	1200	1661	2.0	92% @ 10,000	[236]
Trimetallic layered MOF-CNT Composite	1 M KOH	23.6	501.5	978.54	2.0	86.1% @ 10,000	[237]
Modified Ni-Co-MOF	Na ₂ SO ₄	103.1	859.1	835.5	1.0	93.9% @ 10,000	[238]
Ni _n Co _m MOFs Composite	1 M KOH	28	444	97	0.5	83% @ 2000	[112]
Mn/Ni-MOF@MWCNTs	1 M LiOH	33.2	1198	793.6	1.0	78.3% @ 2000	[170]
FeCu(BDC)/MWCNTs	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	151.07	523.45	986.6	1.0	93.7% @ 10,000	[239]
BC-Fe-Ni Composites	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	18.3	350	320.5	0.5	108% @ 10,000	[240]
Ni-Fe-O/NPC@PCNFs	3 M KOH	41.3	892.2	1419	1.0	78.6% @ 20,000	[192]
NiCo MOF@NiCo CNF	2 M KOH	45.4	800	127.7	1.0	70% @ 4000	[174]
Metal Oxide/Hydroxide Derived Bimetallic MOF Based Composites							
S-MnCo-MOF-74@MnCo LDH	1 M KOH	148.7	700	1875.4	1.0	78.3% @ 5000	[241]
NiCo ₂ O ₄ /β-Ni _x Co _{1-x} (OH) ₂ /α-Ni _x Co _{1-x} (OH) ₂ ternary composite	PVA/KOH hydrogel	36.98	801.49	1315	5.0	90.7% @ 10,000	[187]
NiCo ₂ O ₄ /NiO	KOH	22.1	4518.6	726	1.0	91.4% @ 5000	[179]
NiCo-MOF-2 Nanowires	KOH	45.7	450.6	108.5	0.5	84.3% @ 6500	[181]
NiO/NiCo ₂ O ₄	6 M KOH	79	240	2461	1.0	78.73% @ 4500	[190]
Co ₃ O ₄ /NiO nanostructures derived from BMOF	1 M KOH	27.28	380	2836	1.0	99.53% @ 9500	[242]
CoV-Trimesic-H3IMDC MOF	1 M KOH	70.65	835	1635.6	1.0	92.1 @ 10,000	[189]
MnFe ₂ -MOF	2 M KOH	32.67	1000	91.87	1.0	85.25% @ 10,000	[188]
ZnCo ₂ O ₄ composites	6 M KOH	28.6	100	94.4	1.0	87.2% @ 5000	[243]
Bimetallic Co ₁ Ag ₃ -MOF	2 M KOH	75.63	566.4	2646	1.0	92.45 @ 12,000	[105]
Core@shell Mn@Al-MOF	2 M KOH	27.26	225	844	1.0	81% @ 10,000	[244]
Cu-Co MOF derived CuO-Co ₃ O ₄	2 M KOH	48.75	750	1564.4	1.0	91.2% @ 10,000	[212]
Chalcogenide-Based BOF composites							
NiCo ₂ S ₄ -Ni ₉ S ₈ -C DYMs	6 M KOH	51	1399.4	293.6	1.0	87.3% @ 5000	[132]
CuCoSe@rGO-NF	KOH	19.8	750	1521.6	1.0	86.2% @ 6000	[149]
(CuCo)Se/NC	2 M KOH	16.3	155.3	121.4	1.0	96% @ 5000	[212]
NiCoSe//Modified activated carbon	3 M KOH	28.78	2.571	177.2	3.0	83.31% @ 3000	[245]
Ni-Zn-Co-Se@rGO/NF	2 M KOH	74.6	796.91	464.4	1.0	96.4% @ 7000	[211]
NiCoSe ₂ /Fe-NiCoSe ₂ YSBs	3 M KOH	76.5	2378.7	1091.2	1.0	85% @ 5000	[246]
NiFeSe@NiFe-MOF	1 M KOH	61.0	5060.0	1772.9	1.0	99.7% @ 5000	[247]
Ni-Fe-Mn-Se nano boxes	1 M KOH	66.8	791	1433	1.0	85% @ 8000	[207]
NiTe@ZIF-67	3 M KOH	45.3	5689.1	1521	1.0	93.5% @ 5000	[248]
Cu-Co-S@MnO ₂	PVA/KOH	185.25	750	1483.3	1.0	93% @ 10,000	[249]
BiCe MOF@MoS ₂	2 M KOH	20.12	799.47	510	1.0	92% @ 4500	[250]
Metal Phosphide-Based BMOF Composites							
(Ni-Fe)-P-C@HCNFs	3 M KOH	62.7	8238.2	1392	1.0	89% @ 10,000	[224]
Ni _x Co _{1-x} P Hollow nanocages	2 M KOH	31.52	700	115.8	1.0	98.3% @ 10,000	[228]
NiCoP/rGO hollow nanocomposite	3 M KOH	60.6	749	1153	1.0	83.7% @ 10,000	[225]
NiCoP composites	6 M KOH	36.87	2250	1456	2.0	87% @ 2000	[217]
NiCoP Microflowers	2 M KOH	48.4	272	1153	1.0	97% @ 7000	[218]
CNT-C(ZnP ₂ @CoP)	1 M KOH	83.03	749.9	265	1.0	94.64% @ 20,000	[230]
Ni _x Co _{2-x} P/C nanohybrids	2 M KOH	47.6	798.9	775.7	1.0	78.1% @ 10,000	[251]
Conductive Polymers-based BMOFs composites							
NiCu-MOF/PANI//AC	3 M KOH	47.12	1237	1447	1.0	94.8% @ 15,000	[42]
PPy@NiCo-CAT	2 M KOH	22.22	400	572.2	1.0	93.68% @ 10,000	[252]

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Electrode Composition	Electrolyte	E_{max} (Wh/kg)	P at E_{max} (W/kg)	Max C_{sp} (F/g)	Current density (A/g)	C_{sp} @cycle	Ref
ZCO@PPy@MXHCNF	3 M KOH	61.3	796.8	1567.5	1.0	92.8% @ 10,000	[253]
SGO/ZIF-67/ZIF-8/POAP	–	114.6	1001.2	825	2.0	90% @ 1000	[254]
Zn/Ni-MOF@PPy	3 M KOH	50.9	1338	160.1	1.0	80% @ 5000	[255]
NiCo-MOF@PNTs	2 M KOH	41.2	375	1109	0.5	79.1% @ 10,000	[256]
CuCe-MOF@PANI-1	6 M KOH	87.45	850	724.4	1.0	88.4% @ 10,000	[257]

Table notes: C_{sp} : specific capacitance, E_{max} (Wh/kg) is the highest recorded energy density in the article, and P is the power density.

Table 3

Effect of addition a second metal to monometallic MOF structures.

Bimetallic MOF	Organic linker	Monometallic counterpart	Benefits of bimetallic system	Ref
Co-Ni-PTA	(p-benzenedicarboxylic acid (PTA))	Ni-PTA, Co-PTA	Co insertion into Ni-MOF shortens Co/Ni-centered bond distances (stronger bonding) lead to faster charge transfer and higher electrical conductivity	[99]
Ni-Co-BTC	(1,3,5-benzenetricarboxylic acid (BTC))	Ni-BTC, Co-BTC	increasing Co content makes nanorods slimmer (higher accessible surface/shorter paths), metal-metal synergy with morphology coupling improves kinetics and stability.	[258]
Ni-Co-DATP	4,4'-diamino- <i>p</i> -terphenyl (DATP)	Ni-DATP, Co-DATP	mixed-metal nodes change the electronic environment and valence distribution, providing more effective redox utilization with improved kinetics	[259]
Ni-Fe-BDC	(terephthalic acid (H ₂ BDC))	Ni-BDC	Fe ³⁺ incorporation provides stronger coordination and promotes defect formation due to different metal-ligand coordination strengths that increases active sites.	[260]
Ni-Fe-BDC	BDC	Fe-BDC	Adding Ni improved the number of electroactive sites and electrolyte ion movement	[261]
Cu-Ni-BDC	BDC	Ni-BDC	Addition of Cu made the regularly oriented morphology and the modulated conductivity	[262]
Zn-Ni-PTA	PTA	Ni-PTA	Zn partially substitutes Ni in the framework, causing lattice/peak shifts consistent with ionic-size-driven substitution and morphology evolution (nanosheets to flower-like microspheres) which lead to improved charge storage	[263]
Co/Ni-BDC and Zn/Ni-BDC	BDC	Ni-BDC	Improved morphology (nanosheet with flower like structure compared to nanosheets only for pristine Ni-MOF), higher specific surface area (>400 m ² /g for Co doping and > 350 m ² /g for Zn doping compared to Ni-MOF (295 m ² /g)), and pore increase, which will enlarge the electrode and electrolyte contact area and shorten the path length for ion transport and mitigated phase transformation during cycling when a second metal is introduced.	[172]
Ni-Co-2mIM	(2-methylimidazole (2mIM))	Co-2mIM	Addition of Ni increase pseudocapacitive activity and more accessible redox sites and better kinetics enabled by the engineered nanoflake/hollow architecture and heterometal incorporation.	[264]
Fe-Co-PCN-250	(3,3',5,5'-Azobenzene tetracarboxylic acid (H ₄ ABTC))	Fe-PCN-250	introducing Co into the Fe ₃ cluster creates more active "open" sites, become most active catalytic site, and lowers computed kinetic barriers for O ₃ decomposition	[265]
Co-Fe-TCPP	(tetra(4-carboxyphenyl) porphine chloride (TCPP))	Fe-TCPP	Fe metal can provide redox/catalytic functionality while the Co metal tunes coordination environment / charge distribution / accessible active centers in the sheet. There is an orbital/charge redistribution and site differentiation when moving from mono-metal to dual-metal nodes.	[266]
Zn-Co-2mIM	2mIM	Zn-2mIM and Co-2mIM	different metal/ligand formation kinetics can be exploited to create spatially controlled metal distributions (partial/segmented heterometal incorporation). With second metal, we can engineer interfaces between chemically distinct node environments inside one crystal, which alters transport/reactivity vs uniform mono-metal nodes.	[65]
Co-Zn-tz	(1,2,4-triazole (tz))	Co-tz and Zn-tz	adding Zn changes the electronic landscape so that electron transfer can be mediated ("self-shuttle"), improving activity and stability vs mono-metal analogues.	[267]
Ni-Cu-BHT	benzenhexathiolato (BHT)	Ni-BHT and Cu-BHT	mixing metals induces a periodic in-plane metal arrangement + bilayer structure, which boosts film crystallinity, with larger/more oriented grains and higher electrical conductivity.	[268]

respectively at a current density of 1 A/g. The electrochemical performance of NiCo BMOF at pH 6.0 was found to be maximum due to the optimal concentration of H⁺ ions on its surface, combined with the formation of unique feather-like morphology that enhances ion diffusion. Furthermore, the ASC device delivered the energy density of 20.4 Wh/kg with the capacitance retention of 87.50% after 2500 cycles. Additionally, the appropriate selection of bimetallic combinations further influences the electrochemical performance [274]. For instance, Ni/Co and Ni/Zn-based BMOFs synthesized using benzene-1,3,5-tricarboxylic acid (BTC) as the organic linker exhibited specific capacities of 263.8 and 203.3 mAh/g at 2.5 A/g, with remarkable cycling stabilities of 95.5 and 92.2% capacitance retention after 5000 cycles, respectively. The assembled symmetric cell exhibited the energy density

of 48.6 Wh/kg and 25.0 Wh/kg for Ni/Co-BTC and Ni/Zn-BTC at 2500 W/kg, respectively.

Moreover, solvent selection plays a critical role in tailoring BMOF morphology and capacitive behavior [144]. Ni/Co-BMOFs synthesized using a 3,5-diaminobenzoic (DABA) linker in organic solvents with varying polarities and deprotonation ability (methanol, ethanol, and *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF)) exhibited distinct morphological transformations. As the solvent deprotonation degree increased, the morphology gradually changed from smooth rod-shaped solid structure to rough hydrangea-like architectures. Among the three, the DMF-assisted synthesis produced highly porous BMOF with the maximum specific capacitance of 621 C/g at 1 A/g, along with the capacitance retention of 81.05% after 5000 cycles. Overall, these findings show that

supercapacitive performance of BMOFs is not only governed by a single parameter but by the collective interplay of metal-ion synergy, composition, organic linker chemistry, and synthesis conditions (pH, and solvent). Carefully engineered structures are therefore required to achieve optimal electrochemical performance.

4.2. Morphology

The electrochemical performance of electrode materials is strongly dependent on their morphology, which directly affects surface area, pore architecture, electron-/ion-transport pathways, and mechanical integrity. For BMOFs-based electrodes, various morphological attributes—ranging from two-dimensional (2D) nanosheets and one-dimensional (1D) nanofibers to core-shell and hierarchical three-dimensional (3D) architectures—directly modulate electrode/electrolyte interface phenomena, charge transfer kinetics, and electrochemical stability [274,275]. Indeed, systematic surface and statistical morphological analyses reveal that controlling the shape, size, and hierarchical arrangement of BMOF crystals can optimize the accessibility of redox-active sites and shorten ion-diffusion distances, thereby enhancing both capacitance and rate capability [274]. Moreover, morphology-tailored BMOFs often achieve synergistic electronic and ionic effects through bimetallic centers dispersed over well-defined geometries, further contributing to pseudocapacitive behavior and cycling durability [98,276].

Two-dimensional (2D) morphology of BMOFs in the form of nanosheets maximize surface-to-volume ratio and expose abundant metal-ligand sites for Faradaic reactions, yielding high specific capacitance and rapid ion kinetics [180]. NiCo-MOF nanosheets with thicknesses between 1.74 and 3.87 nm exhibits a remarkable capacitance of 1202 F/g at 1 A/g, outperforming bulk analogues by over 60% due to shortened ion diffusion paths and enhanced conductivity across stacked nanosheets. These 2D morphologies are responsible for facilitating electron percolation along the plane of the sheets, reducing resistive losses at high current densities, leading to capacitance retention of 54% at a current density of 50 A/g [180]. A similar value of capacitance of 1178 C/g at 2 mA cm⁻² was noted from ultrathin-nanosheet morphology of Mn-doped Ni-MOFs grown on Ni foam substrate which is attributed to the increased density of surface redox sites and rapid ion transport across the nanosheet interfaces [277]. Despite significant features of 2D morphology, restacking of nanosheets can impede ion accessibility. To circumvent, strategies such as intercalating conductive spacers or orienting sheets vertically on current collectors have been developed to preserve open channels. Directly grown oriented nanosheets over a substrate offer binder-free electrode architecture, provide good electrical contact and possibility of high mass loadings without compromising ion-accessibility. For example, triethylamine-assisted vertically aligned arrays of Ni/Co-MOFs nanosheets over a Ni foam achieves hierarchical interconnected network delivering capacitance of 1952 F/g at 1 A/g, with capacitance retention of 69.1% at 3 A/g [278]. Such vertical orientation causes diffusion channels to accelerate charge transfer kinetics. However, apart from the morphology, it is also important to control the particle size of MOF-derived materials to optimize the supercapacitor performance [279].

One-dimensional (1D) nanofiber supports decorated with BMOF nanosheets have emerged as a versatile strategy to combine mechanical flexibility with high electrochemical performance. Tian et al., engineered preoxidized polyacrylonitrile nanofibers (PPNFs) as scaffolds for BMOF nanosheet growth of M-Ni MOFs, where M = Co, Zn, Cu, Fe, in which PPNFs@Co-Ni-MOF delivered a capacitance of 1096 F/g at 1 A/g and excellent rate performance [275]. This architecture not only enlarged the electrode-electrolyte interface but also provided direct electron-transport channels along the fiber axis. In addition, 1D fiber-2D sheet hybrids prevent the structural collapse that happens with independent sheets and improve rate performance by providing both mechanical support and electron conduction.

Core-shell BMOF designs use sequential growth or seed-mediated epitaxy to put together several frameworks into a single structure with enhanced porosity and channels that act at different scales benefiting superior electrochemical performance. For instance, ZIF-90@ZIF-67 core-shell particles made via seed epitaxy at room temperature achieved a greater specific surface area (1663 m²g⁻¹) and more microporosity than monometallic ZIFs [276]. When used as SC electrodes, the core-shell BMOFs had a specific capacitance of 1358 F/g at 1 A/g and 90% of capacitance retention at 10 A/g after 4000 cycles. This was because of its hierarchical pore network and dual-metal active sites. Morphological analyses confirm that core-shell BMOFs afford multiple adsorption/desorption regimes and homogeneously distributed electron pathways, crucial for balancing high energy and power densities [213,216]. In addition, such hollow BMOF micro-/nanostructures leverage internal cavities to buffer volume changes during electrochemical cycling and expose both interior and exterior surfaces for charge-storage. For example, Zhang et al., reported hollow Ni/Co-MOF spheres with uniformly distributed protrusions, synthesized via a one-pot solvothermal route, which exhibited a specific capacitance of 828 C/g at 1 A/g and 82% retention after 5000 cycles [280]. This hollow architecture reduced diffusion lengths and served as "ion reservoirs," ensuring rapid electrolyte infiltration and efficient utilization of redox-active sites. Similarly, self-assembled Ni-doped Co-MOF spherical shells, when directly grown on Ni foam, afforded 664 F/g at 1 A/g and exceptional cycling stability (96% retention over 10,000 cycles), attributed to the mechanical resilience of the shell structure and its high accessible surface area [281].

Hierarchical three-dimensional (3D) architectures—such as nanourchin or nanoflower arrays—further amplify electrode performance by integrating macro-, meso-, and micropores into a single construct. Zhou et al., transformed ZIF-67 into a 3D hierarchical NiCo layered-double-hydroxide (LDH) nanosheet on copper cobalt carbonate (CoCu) urchin-like skeleton with a high mass loading of 14 mg cm⁻² on Ni foam, achieving a specific capacitance of 1346 F/g at 3 mA cm⁻² and 87% rate capability at 50 mA cm⁻² [282]. The radially aligned nanourchins on nanosheet bases provided abundant electrochemically active sites and facilitated efficient ion diffusion through interlinked channels. Moreover, template-free etching of Zn₃₃Co₆₇-ZIF by ethylene glycol generated hierarchical micro-mesoporous carbons upon carbonization, yielded electrodes with a capacitance increase of 45% and a rate capability improvement of 67% at a scan rate from 1 to 100 mV/s, highlighting importance of hierarchical morphology in optimizing ion transport and electronic conductivity [283]. Specifically, hierarchical morphology in the form of raspberry-like or flower-like assemblies provide high active-site exposure with efficient electrolyte percolation. For example, Zhang et al., synthesized raspberry-like NiCo-MOF particles by tuning nucleation and growth rates, achieving a hierarchical rough surface that delivered 640 F/g at 1 A/g [284]. Such morphology is desirable where interparticle voids facilitate rapid ion diffusion. Similarly, flower-like Ni/Co-MOFs synthesized by a solvothermal method exhibited a capacitance of 882 F/g at 0.5 A/g and maintained 90% capacitance retention after 3000 charge-discharge cycles at 5 A/g. Their petal-like features provide a smooth transmission channel for electrons and ions transport [285].

4.3. Electrolytes

In BMOF-based SCs, the electrolyte should be considered an active design component affecting ion conductivity, the accessible voltage window, redox reversibility, charge transfer resistance, desolvation barrier, pore accessibility, structural stability of the framework, and long-term electrode/electrolyte compatibility [243,286]. This is particularly important for BMOFs because their charge-storage often combines electric double-layer capacitance with Faradaic reactions involving two metal centers. Therefore, electrolyte ions must simultaneously satisfy several requirements i.e., they must be sufficiently

mobile, small or deformable enough after partial desolvation to enter the pores, chemically compatible with the metal/ligand framework or derived phase, and able to support reversible charge compensation at the active metal sites.

A critical but often under-discussed parameter is the difference between the bare ionic radius and the hydrated or solvated radius. In aqueous electrolytes, ions do not migrate as isolated species, they carry hydration shells whose size and binding strength strongly affect their ability to enter MOF pores or interlayer galleries. For example, Li^+ has a small crystallographic radius but a strongly bound hydration shell, which can make its effective hydrated size larger and its desolvation more energy-demanding than K^+ . By contrast, K^+ is more weakly hydrated and often displays faster transport in alkaline pseudocapacitive systems. Thus, the performance trend in alkaline electrolytes cannot be interpreted only from bare ion size. It reflects a balance among hydrated radius, hydration energy, ion mobility, and the interaction of OH^- with redox-active metal centers. In BMOFs containing Ni, Co, Mn, or Fe, alkaline electrolytes are often preferred because OH^- participates directly in surface redox reactions such as $\text{M-OH}/\text{M-OOH}$ conversion. However, stronger alkalinity may also accelerate ligand hydrolysis, framework reconstruction, or dissolution of labile metal sites. Therefore, the best electrolyte is not necessarily the most concentrated or most alkaline one; it is the one that provides fast redox kinetics without destroying the coordination framework.

Recent mechanistic work on conductive MOF SCs provides useful design rules that are directly transferable to BMOF systems. Gittins et al., showed that the cation size in tetraalkylammonium-based organic electrolytes strongly affects the capacitive behavior of $\text{Cu}_3(\text{HHTP})_2$ MOF [287]. Larger cations led to pore saturation and stronger charging asymmetry, while smaller ions produced higher energy-storage performance. This finding is important for BMOFs because it demonstrates that porosity alone is insufficient: the pores must be accessible to the electrolyte ion in its solvated or partially desolvated state. Similarly, solid-state NMR and operando EQCM studies on $\text{Ni}_3(\text{HITP})_2$ MOF revealed distinct in-pore and ex-pore electrolyte environments and showed that specific chemical interactions between the electrolyte and MOF functional groups govern ion adsorption [111]. These results suggest that

future BMOF studies should report not only BET surface area and pore size distribution, but also whether those pores are electrochemically accessible under realistic electrolyte conditions. The role of pore accessibility becomes even more complex in BMOFs because bimetallic nodes introduce spatially heterogeneous electrostatic environments. Two different metal centers may bind electrolyte ions with different strengths, alter local pH near the interface, or promote inner-sphere adsorption of OH^- , SO_4^{2-} , H^+ , or redox-active species. When such interactions are moderate, they improve ion residence time and redox-site utilization. When they are too strong, they can slow desorption, increase polarization, and reduce rate capability. Operando neutron scattering on conductive MOF micropores has shown that solvent/electrolyte soaking and polarization change the population of species confined in micropores, confirming that electrolyte accessibility under operating conditions can differ from static porosity measurements [288]. For BMOF-based electrodes, this means that hierarchical porosity is essential: micropores provide high surface area and ion adsorption sites, while mesopores and macropores act as electrolyte reservoirs that shorten diffusion pathways and reduce concentration gradients during fast charging.

Aqueous alkaline electrolytes such as KOH, NaOH, and LiOH remain the most widely used electrolytes for BMOF-based pseudocapacitive electrodes because they offer high ionic conductivity, low viscosity, low cost, and fast OH^- -mediated redox kinetics. However, the relative performance of KOH, NaOH, and LiOH is material-dependent. For instance, Chu et al., [286] investigated the performance of CoNi-MOF electrodes in 1 M solution of KOH, NaOH, and LiOH electrolytes (Fig. 14). In 1 M KOH, the CV curve showed the largest area and smallest peak voltage difference (0.21 V), indicating high capacitance and strong redox reversibility (Fig. 14a). Similarly, longer charge-discharge time in GCD plots (Fig. 14b) was observed in 1 M KOH delivering the highest specific capacitance of 833.3 F/g at 1 A/g. This value was retained to 81.1% even at a high current density of 16 A/g (Fig. 14c). Furthermore, this electrode maintained 90.9% capacity after 10,000 charge-discharge cycles in KOH electrolyte which showed far superior to LiOH and NaOH electrolytes due to smaller K^+ hydration radius (Fig. 14d). On the other hand, the relatively larger hydrated ionic radius of Li^+ and Na^+ ,

Fig. 14. Electrochemical performance comparison of CoNi-MOF electrode in 1 M LiOH, 1 M NaOH and 1 M KOH aqueous electrolytes: (a) CV curves at 20 mV/s, (b) GCD curves at 1 A g⁻¹, (c) specific capacitance, and (d) cyclic stability. (Reproduced with permission [286], Copyright 2022, IOP publishing).

resulting in volume expansion and structural collapse of the electroactive materials during electrochemical testing. Overall, the smaller hydration radius and higher mobility of K^+ relative to Na^+ and Li^+ facilitate faster OH^- insertion/extraction at the redox couples, yielding superior specific capacitance and rate capability in 1 M KOH. However, the intrinsic water-splitting limit (~ 1.2 V) confines the maximum operating voltage, capping the energy density achievable with purely aqueous systems. Similarly, ZnCo BMOF@rGO composites have been systematically evaluated in both alkaline (KOH, NaOH, and LiOH) and neutral electrolytes (K_2SO_4 , Na_2SO_4 , and Li_2SO_4). Among all the electrolytes, the composite delivered the highest capacitive performance in NaOH electrolyte (1627.21 F/g at 0.5 A/g). This enhanced behavior is attributed to the high concentration and strong nucleophilicity of OH^- ions, which promote redox reactions, improve ionic transport, and provide additional pseudo-capacitance contribution relative to neutral electrolytes [289].

Concentration of the electrolyte also affects the performance of SCs; therefore, it must be optimized as per the system. Increasing hydroxide concentration can enhance ionic conductivity and redox kinetics up to a point, but excessive concentration increases viscosity, slows ion diffusion, raises polarization, and may accelerate framework degradation. A recent Co-MOF electrolyte study showed that 1 M NaOH outperformed more concentrated NaOH solutions, illustrating that higher alkalinity does not automatically translate to better performance [290]. Neutral aqueous electrolytes such as Na_2SO_4 , K_2SO_4 , and Li_2SO_4 are attractive when long-term stability and wider cell voltage are more important than maximum pseudocapacitive current [291,292]. Neutral electrolytes are also generally less corrosive than strongly acidic or alkaline electrolytes and can be gentler toward fragile MOF frameworks. This point is important because many MOFs do not retain their structure under strongly alkaline aqueous conditions; Zheng et al., explicitly noted that most MOFs hardly maintain their physical and chemical properties after exposure to alkaline solutions, which motivated the design of alkaline-stable MOF composites for electrochemical energy storage [293]. Also, neutral electrolytes often provide weaker Faradaic activation for Ni-, Co-, or Mn-based pseudocapacitive centers than alkaline electrolytes, because OH^- activity is lower and OH^- is directly involved in many transition-metal redox processes. This is consistent with electrolyte-comparison studies on MOF electrodes, where conventional Na_2SO_4 generally gives lower pseudocapacitive response than acidic/redox or alkaline electrolytes, while KOH/NaOH systems more strongly activate metal-centered redox couples [294,295]. Moreover, multivalent or strongly hydrated anions such as SO_4^{2-} may show slower pore diffusion and stronger interfacial adsorption than monovalent ions. Therefore, neutral electrolytes are better suited to BMOFs or BMOF-derived carbons where EDLC-type storage dominates, while alkaline electrolytes are generally more suitable when reversible transition-metal redox chemistry is the main capacitance source. Acidic electrolytes such as H_2SO_4 can provide very high proton mobility and fast surface charge compensation. However, they must be used cautiously with BMOFs because many metal-carboxylate or metal-imidazolite bonds are unstable under acidic conditions. Acidic media may protonate ligands, dissolve metal nodes, or cause irreversible structural reconstruction. For chemically stable MOFs or MOF-derived oxides/carbons, acidic electrolytes can be beneficial, but for pristine BMOFs the electrolyte stability window must be evaluated together with post-cycling structural characterization. The recent Ni-BDC MOF study using H_2SO_4/KI redox electrolyte showed that acidic redox media can strongly enhance capacitance, but the enhancement arises from both proton mobility and iodide-mediated Faradaic reactions [294]. Such results should therefore be compared carefully with conventional electrolytes because the electrolyte itself contributes charge-storage.

In a recent study, introducing redox-active species into the alkaline electrolyte has emerged as an effective strategy to enhance capacitive performance, as these additives provide additional Faradaic redox couples. Additives such as I^-/I_3^- , $Fe(CN)_6^{3-}/Fe(CN)_6^{4-}$, quinone/

hydroquinone, and transition-metal redox couples introduce additional solution-phase Faradaic reactions. The porous $NiCo_2O_4/rGO$, prepared by transforming ZIF-67/rGO, were evaluated in an electrolyte containing potassium ferricyanide ($K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$) (PFC) and NaOH [296]. The assembled symmetric SC device exhibited the energy density of 75.54 Wh/kg at a power density of 1.6 kW/kg at 0.5 A/g. Interestingly, the energy density was enhanced by 2.5-fold when 0.3 M of PFC was introduced into 3 M NaOH. This study shows that the introduction of redox-active electrolytes has proven to be effective in enhancing the charge-storage performance. However, redox electrolytes can also increase self-discharge, cause mediator crossover, corrode current collectors, or obscure the intrinsic capacitance of the electrode. Therefore, when redox electrolytes are used in BMOF-based SCs, authors should explicitly distinguish electrode capacitance from electrolyte-mediated capacitance and should report coulombic efficiency, leakage current, self-discharge, and long-term chemical stability.

Ionic liquids (ILs) and high-concentration organic electrolytes are different from dilute aqueous electrolytes because their large, often poorly solvated ions and high ionic strength alter the electric double layer, promote partial desolvation in confined pores and enable ion layering or overscreening at charged surfaces. Also, they provide wider electrochemical windows than aqueous electrolytes and can therefore increase energy density because energy scales with the square of voltage. However, their practical benefit depends strongly on ion size, viscosity, and desolvation behavior inside the pores. Organic electrolytes usually contain bulky solvated ions, and ionic liquids consist entirely of large ions with strong ion-ion correlations. These features can limit ion diffusion in narrow MOF micropores, particularly at high current density. Experiments that impregnate ILs into ZIF-8 show dramatic increases in ion conductivity and altered activation energies consistent with confinement-induced desolvation and enhanced ion mobility within rigid pore networks [297]. Reviews and mechanistic studies highlight that ILs can also stabilize unusual oxidation states at metal sites through specific ion-metal interactions, lowering activation barriers for reversible redox and extending cycle life in MOF-derived electrodes [298,299]. Molecular dynamics simulations of conductive MOF electrodes with ionic-liquid electrolytes have shown that capacitance depends on how ions reside inside polarized MOF pores and how rapidly they reorganize during charging [300,301]. Thus, ionic liquids should be matched with BMOFs that have sufficiently large, connected, and electronically conductive pores. In this regard, bimetallic conductive MOFs and BMOF-derived carbons/chalcogenides/phosphides with hierarchical mesoporosity may be better candidates for ionic-liquid electrolytes than narrow-pore pristine MOFs. Organic solvent-based electrolytes, by contrast, offer higher ionic mobility but require pore sizes and surface chemistry that avoid excessive solvation shells. A balance that bimetallic architectures can tune i.e., mixed metal nodes can provide a distribution of binding strengths and local polarities so that one metal may preferentially coordinate anions while the other stabilizes cation adsorption or mediates inner-sphere redox transitions, enabling simultaneous double-layer and pseudocapacitive storage pathways. Molecular dynamics and first-principles modelling further corroborate these observations by showing that ion size, shape and electronic polarizability determine how ions approach and bind to metal-ligand motifs [302]. Heterometallic SBUs with differing metal-oxygen bond strengths produce spatially varying electrostatic potentials that direct ion placement and local solvation structure, the atomic origins of the observed macroscopic increases in capacitance, rate capability and redox activity. Collectively, more studies are needed on BMOFs with ionic-liquid and organic electrolytes. The available computational studies establish a mechanistic framework: electrolyte chemistry (ionic liquid vs. organic) and MOF composition act together to set ion occupancy, desolvation energetics and site-specific redox thermodynamics at the interface, and it is this atomic-scale interplay that underpins the enhanced electrochemical performance observed for MOF-based SCs [303].

Gel polymer electrolytes, especially PVA/KOH, PVA/H₂SO₄, and PVA/Na₂SO₄, are increasingly used in flexible and wearable BMOF-based devices. Their main advantages are leakage prevention, mechanical compliance, simplified packaging, and improved safety. However, gel electrolytes usually have lower ionic conductivity and slower ion diffusion than liquid electrolytes because ion motion is coupled to polymer-chain dynamics and water retention. For BMOF electrodes, this means that nanosheet, nanowire, hollow, or vertically aligned architectures are preferable because they reduce tortuosity and maintain electrode/electrolyte contact under bending. Pouch-type Ni—Co MOF asymmetric devices and Cu@Fe-MOF gel-electrolyte devices demonstrate the promise of PVA/KOH systems, but their performance should be interpreted in terms of practical stability and mechanical reliability, not only capacitance [235,304]. Electrolyte choice also differs between pristine BMOFs and BMOF-derived materials. In pristine BMOFs, electrolyte stability is governed by the strength of metal–ligand bonds, framework hydrophilicity, and resistance to protonation or hydroxide attack. Strong acid or base can partially destroy the framework, even if the capacitance initially increases. In BMOF-derived materials, such as mixed oxides, hydroxides, sulfides, selenides, and phosphides, the original coordination framework is no longer the primary stability constraint. Instead, electrolyte compatibility depends on phase stability, surface reconstruction, vacancy chemistry, and dissolution of metal species. For example, Ni—Co phosphides or sulfides in alkaline electrolyte may undergo surface oxidation to active oxyhydroxide-like layers during cycling, and OH[−] adsorption/desorption becomes central to charge storage [106]. In such cases, the electrolyte actively participates in forming the true working surface. Therefore, post-cycling XPS, Raman, XRD, and electron microscopy are necessary to determine whether the reported capacitance arises from the original BMOF-derived phase or from an electrochemically reconstructed surface.

Overall, electrolyte selection for BMOF-based SCs should follow a structure–electrolyte matching principle. For redox-active pristine BMOFs, alkaline electrolytes can maximize pseudocapacitance but require framework stability against hydrolysis. Neutral electrolytes may improve voltage window and durability but can reduce Faradaic kinetics. Acidic electrolytes offer high proton conductivity but may destabilize many coordination frameworks. Organic electrolytes and ionic liquids expand the voltage window but demand larger, connected, and conductive pores to overcome sluggish ion diffusion. Redox-active electrolytes can dramatically increase apparent capacitance but complicate mechanistic interpretation and long-term stability. Therefore, future reports should not merely list the electrolyte used; they should justify the choice based on hydrated/solvated ion size, desolvation energy, pore accessibility, redox compatibility, voltage stability, and post-cycling structural integrity. This electrolyte-centered analysis is essential for translating BMOF-based electrodes from high capacitance in three-electrode tests to reliable high-energy and long-life practical supercapacitor devices.

5. Challenges and future perspectives in the development of BMOFs for SCs

Despite their promising performance enhancements over monometallic MOFs in catalysis, adsorption, and energy conversion, BMOFs still face several core limitations that hinder broader application and scalability. A major challenge is the precise control of metal composition and distribution at the atomic scale. Conventional one-pot solvothermal syntheses often struggle to yield uniform stoichiometry and homogeneous metal site distribution, with metal centers incorporating into the framework inconsistently relative to the initial feed ratios, complicating reproducibility and structure–property relationships [305]. Moreover, metal ion leaching and structural instability under operational conditions remain critical hurdles; for example, Fe-MIL-88B exhibits substantial iron leaching and framework degradation under oxidative conditions, while suitably doped bimetallic variants show far lower

leaching only after careful compositional engineering [306]. In aqueous catalytic environments, the recycling and long-term durability of BMOFs can be limited by particle instability and difficulty in recovery, impacting their practical reuse [307]. Additionally, although bimetallic architectures can improve active site density and functional tunability, synthesis protocols can be highly sensitive to reaction parameters (e.g., pH, ligand chemistry, and temperature), often requiring extensive optimization for each metal pair and linker combination, a factor that impedes rapid screening and scale-up.

Other critical challenges include the complexity of scalable synthesis, and structural instability during long-term cycling of certain frameworks. Many reported BMOFs and derivative syntheses rely on multi-step routes, which can hinder scale-up for industrial applications [308]. Apart from synthesis issues, controlled construction of hierarchical BMOF architectures remains a central challenge for SC applications. Introducing well-defined multiscale porosity and spatially ordered metal distributions within a single framework is still largely empirical, as conventional one-pot syntheses provide limited control over pore hierarchy, defect gradients, and metal-site arrangement [309]. Drawing from hierarchical MOF design principles, future BMOF development will require modular and stepwise assembly strategies capable of programming structural and compositional order across multiple length scales, thereby enabling cooperative ion transport and redox processes. Equally important is the advancement of high-resolution and operando characterization techniques to resolve hierarchical features, mixed-metal site distributions, and their dynamic evolution during electrochemical cycling, which currently hampers quantitative structure–performance correlations. For instance, operando characterization has recently begun to elucidate fundamental charge-storage mechanisms in model MOF electrodes. For instance, operando small-angle X-ray scattering of Ni₃(HITP)₂ electrodes has revealed immobilization of electrolyte anions at pore walls and cation-dominated charge-storage under bias, providing a rare window into in situ ion dynamics and structural evolution during cycling [310].

Despite this progress, mechanistic insight into bimetallic architectures remains limited. In particular, the roles of defect populations, mixed-metal sites, and hybrid interfaces in governing capacitance, rate capability, and long-term stability are still described largely qualitatively rather than quantitatively. To address this, synergistic integration of experimental operando studies with advanced modelling and machine learning is essential. Machine learning models have already begun to correlate structural descriptors with performance metrics in MOF SCs, identifying SSA and porosity as dominant factors in capacitance and charging kinetics [311]. Such integrated approaches will be critical to define clear structure/function relationships that guide rational design and scalable, green synthesis routes (e.g., solvent-free, low-energy or bio-assisted methods) for BMOF-based electrodes, ultimately bridging the current divide between laboratory innovation and industrial implementation. Further, theoretical insights and data-driven approaches can be effective to minimize the trial-and-error synthesis, accelerate material optimization, guide rationale design of BMOFs, and accelerate the development of high-performance SC devices [312,313].

Despite the promising electrochemical properties of BMOFs and their derived composites for SC applications, long-term cyclability and structural integrity remain critical challenges. Many BMOF-derived electrodes suffer from framework degradation, volume change-induced stress, and partial dissolution of redox-active species under repeated charge–discharge cycles, leading to capacity fading and loss of active surface area. Studies on MOF-derived electrodes suggest that poor structural robustness and mechanical instability are intrinsically linked to the inherent low conductivity and moderate chemical stability of many coordination frameworks, which further exacerbates cycling degradation under real SC conditions [314]. To overcome these limitations, rational modulation of interfacial chemistry, defect engineering within hybrid architectures, and strategic hybridization with conductive hosts are needed to suppress volume expansion, stabilize redox centers,

and enhance electron/ion transport pathways. For instance, oriented nanosheet arrays in Ni/Co-MOFs have demonstrated improved charge transfer kinetics and mitigated structural distortion, leading to enhanced cycle retention [278]. In parallel with electrode design, electrolyte engineering is essential to expand the operational voltage window and energy density beyond what is achievable with conventional aqueous media. Non-aqueous systems like organic electrolytes and ionic liquids are known to enable wider electrochemical windows and higher energy storage, improving SC performance, though their high viscosity and slower ion dynamics require careful optimization of ion transport within MOF pore structures [315]. Solid-state and gel polymer electrolytes also offer routes toward enhanced safety and mechanical robustness in flexible or wearable SC devices if integrated compatibly with BMOF electrodes.

A major future direction for BMOF-based SCs is the development of practically relevant thick electrodes without sacrificing rate capability. Most reported BMOF electrodes are evaluated at low active-material loading, where short ion-diffusion lengths and abundant electrolyte access can overestimate real device performance [316]. In commercial-level electrodes, however, increasing mass loading inevitably increases electrode thickness, tortuosity, and internal resistance, causing incomplete utilization of buried redox sites and a sharp decrease in capacitance at high current density. This problem is particularly serious for BMOFs because their pseudocapacitive response depends on simultaneous electron transport through the framework/derivative phase and ion transport through hierarchical pores. Therefore, future work should move beyond ultrathin coatings or low-loading powders and instead focus on thick, binder-free, mechanically integrated architectures with continuous conductive backbones, vertically aligned ion channels, and controlled *meso*/macroporosity. Promising strategies include MOF-derived carbon frameworks, self-supported macroscopic structures including conductive foams/fibers/aerogels, electrophoretic deposition, laser-patterned electrodes, and 3D-printed architectures all of which are valuable because they can decouple high mass loading from sluggish ion transport. Recent studies on commercial-level mass loading emphasize that electrodes above $\sim 10 \text{ mg cm}^{-2}$ are essential for practical SCs, but their success depends on maintaining ion permeation, charge transfer, and redox-reaction kinetics throughout the full electrode thickness [317,318]. Leveraging direct ink writing and other 3D printing modalities enables bespoke electrode designs with tailored pore networks and ion transport pathways, mitigating issues of poor conductivity and mechanical fragility that have historically limited MOF electrode performance [77]. However, translating these techniques to MOF systems remains challenging due to rheological constraints, framework fragility, and limited understanding of how printing parameters affect electrochemical performance [319]. Addressing all these challenges will be essential to transition BMOFs from proof-of-concept materials toward rationally designed, high-performance SC electrodes.

Another issue that needs similar attention is volumetric performance [320]. BMOF-based materials often show impressive gravimetric capacitance because of their high surface area and low skeletal density, yet this does not automatically translate into high volumetric capacitance or device-level energy density. Excessive micro/mesoporosity, low tap density, and loosely packed nanosheet assemblies may improve electrolyte accessibility but reduce the amount of active material per unit electrode volume [321]. This is a critical limitation for compact devices, where volume rather than mass is often the limiting factor. Future studies should therefore report areal and volumetric capacitance, electrode density, thickness, porosity, mass loading, and device packing fraction alongside gravimetric capacitance [322]. For BMOFs, an optimal electrode should not simply maximize BET surface area, it should balance accessible porosity with sufficient packing density and electronic percolation. Dense-but-permeable BMOF-derived carbons, mixed-metal oxides/hydroxides with hierarchical secondary pores, and compressed self-standing films may provide more realistic pathways toward high volumetric energy and power densities than highly fluffy

powder electrodes. Recent discussions based on the actual principles of the field of SC performance metrics, they emphasize that material-level capacitance is insufficient for predicting practical device energy density, while fast-charging studies show that pore-network tortuosity strongly controls ion transport in thick porous electrodes [323,324].

Future BMOF-based SC studies should also evaluate self-discharge and leakage current, which are rarely discussed despite being central to practical energy retention. Self-discharge is generally defined as the spontaneous voltage decay of a charged SC under open-circuit conditions, and recent review classify its main origins as ohmic leakage, Faradaic side reactions, and charge redistribution within porous electrodes [325]. The rich redox chemistry that makes BMOFs attractive can also promote parasitic Faradaic reactions, charge redistribution, metal-ion dissolution, electrolyte decomposition, or shuttle-type processes, especially when redox-active electrolytes or mixed-valence metal sites are used. This concern is well established for redox-electrolyte SCs as hydroquinone-based active electrolytes increase capacitance but accelerate self-discharge through mediator migration, while ferricyanide electrolytes can suffer from large leakage current and self-discharge due to redox shuttling through the separator [326,327]. Defects and oxygen/sulfur/phosphorus vacancies can improve charge-storage, but if poorly stabilized they may also act as sites for unwanted interfacial reactions. This is particularly relevant because recent self-discharge studies show that activation-controlled Faradaic reactions at electrode/electrolyte interfaces can dominate voltage decay even in nominally EDLC-type porous electrodes [328]. Thus, future reports should include open-circuit voltage decay, leakage-current measurements, floating tests, and post-self-discharge chemical analysis, rather than relying only on cycling retention. Float-current and open-circuit-potential methods are widely recognized as complementary approaches for evaluating self-discharge and leakage behavior in electrochemical energy-storage devices [329]. This is particularly important for BMOF-derived sulfides, selenides, phosphides, and oxyhydroxides, where surface reconstruction during cycling can create highly active but chemically dynamic interfaces. A relevant MOF-derived example is the modular Zn-Ni-CoP@CoP nanowire array, where the authors explicitly targeted tip-charge-induced self-discharge and obtained an ultralow leakage current of 10.28 μA , demonstrating that MOF-derived electrode geometry can directly affect leakage behavior [330]. Another useful example is MOF-derived double-shell hollow Ni-Fe-Mn-Se nanocubes, for which the authors reported self-discharge testing and retention of an open-circuit potential of 0.9 V after 20 h, indicating relatively low self-discharge in the assembled ASC device [207]. The goal should be to identify whether self-discharge arises mainly from ohmic leakage, redox shuttle reactions, charge redistribution inside hierarchical pores, or instability of the electrode/electrolyte interface. Such analysis would help distinguish truly stable charge storage behavior from high initial capacitance accompanied by poor energy retention.

Finally, greater emphasis should be placed on full-cell validation, reproducibility, and standardized reporting. Many BMOF studies still rely heavily on three-electrode measurements, which are useful for mechanistic screening but cannot represent practical device behavior. Future reports should validate optimized materials in two-electrode symmetric or asymmetric full cells with realistic electrode balancing, controlled negative/positive mass ratios, practical voltage windows, and device-level energy/power calculations based on the total mass of both electrodes, and preferably including current collectors, separator, and electrolyte where appropriate. A recent article on mass-balancing emphasizes that insufficient attention to positive/negative electrode mass ratios has led to misunderstandings and misuses in asymmetric SC design, especially for pseudocapacitive and hybrid devices [331]. Reproducibility is equally important because BMOF synthesis is highly sensitive to metal-precursor/ligand ratio, ligand deprotonation, pH, solvent composition, reaction temperature, and post-treatment conditions [26]. Small variations can change metal distribution, defect density, morphology, and phase evolution during conversion. Therefore,

future work should include batch-to-batch comparisons, error bars from independently prepared electrodes, clear mass-loading/thickness values, Coulombic efficiency, EIS before and after cycling, and post-mortem structural characterization. Establishing such reporting practices will make BMOF-based SC research more comparable and will help separate genuine structure–relationships from performance variations caused by testing protocols or under-reported device parameters. An interlaboratory study on SC data analysis showed that different laboratories can obtain significantly different reported values from the same electrochemical data because of inconsistent formulae, terminology, and interpretation, with especially large variation for non-ideal capacitive profiles [332]. Similarly, reviews on SC performance evaluation emphasize that inconsistent methods for capacitance, resistance, energy density, and power density can cause confusion in comparing device performance [333,334].

6. Conclusions

This review delineates how bimetallic metal–organic frameworks represent a distinct and chemically programmable class of electrode materials in which dual-metal coordination fundamentally reshapes charge storage behavior. By systematically examining synthetic routes, framework dimensionality and compositional tuning, we show that the incorporation of two dissimilar metal centers alters local coordination environments, electronic structure and defect chemistry, thereby governing redox accessibility, ion transport kinetics and cycling stability. Hierarchical architectures and controlled pore connectivity emerge as critical structural motifs that couple electrolyte infiltration with efficient utilization of redox-active sites, particularly when matched with appropriate aqueous, redox-active or organic/ionic electrolytes. Beyond pristine frameworks, the review establishes that hybridization with conductive architectures such as carbon frameworks, MXenes, layered double hydroxides and conductive polymers, provides a rational pathway to overcome the intrinsic electronic limitations of MOFs by enabling continuous electron transport and mechanically stabilizing redox-active domains. Furthermore, BMOF-derived materials illustrate how framework-encoded composition and morphology can be preserved or deliberately transformed into electrochemically active oxides, hydroxides, chalcogenides, and phosphides with enhanced conductivity and structural robustness. Collectively, the structure–property–performance correlations discussed herein establish a mechanistic foundation for the rational design of high-performance BMOF-based SC electrodes and provide guidance for translating these materials toward durable, scalable energy storage devices.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author used ChatGPT in order to improve the language. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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